

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD⁵ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁸ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020)

Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)¹⁻⁶

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Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)⁴; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh;

Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)³; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre³; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Research product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh;

Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)²; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre²; Fund Approved by City University; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh

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Keynote

This is a six-month duration project completion report at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. The service charge of researcher is discounted due to the minimum approval of the research fund of 1,00,000 BDT. The service charge is also subsidized and self-invested by the chief researcher. The additional costs are claimed to the funder. The publication was circulated at the relevant departments and the relevant expert panels. The quality versus time versus fund versus outcomes

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versus the experience of the chief researcher is proportionally run to the goal of a researcher and/or funder. This project took more time due to the part-time service with the full-time service of the chief researcher. This project had no official study leave/research leave for the chief researcher at City University when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain parallelly performed as chief researcher, consultant, textile engineer, accountant, office assistant, office secretary, and administrative director of the project on dyes and textile coloration. Reasons of the financial crisis of professor community are critically explained in the section of discussion to satisfy the support to extend the support of the relevant community. Numerous limitations of research funding, research profession, higher education quality, and relevant contradictions have been remarked and analyzed for the understanding of funding authorities, universities, and research organizations. This assessment of quality enhancement and professional guideline charge to City University, Bangladesh should be 20,000 USD or one year duration full-time salary of a senior professor in Bangladesh or one year duration full-time salary of a chief researcher in Bangladesh. Therefore, City University may show/display this report for the research fund of Bangladesh government, university grants commission of Bangladesh, board of accreditation for engineering and technical education, Bangladesh accreditation council, institutional quality assurance cell of City University, higher education quality enhancement project (HEQEP), United Nations, and central peer review purposes of the university and/or department of textile engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Outcomes and approach of professional law for the university professors/researchers

1. Every chief researcher should get a prestigious amount of salary or a minimum salary of the equivalent salary of the mother job/main salary or a percentage of salary of lecturer, assistant professor, associate professor, professor, and senior professor at any university to satisfy the research practice to satisfy the research service for the whole project duration in a research project.
2. Every income of chief researcher and relevant expenditure in a research project/research organization/university should be tax free.
3. Every chief professor and chief researcher should have a standard amount of secretary allowance if the chief professor and chief researcher have no secretary. Moreover, a secretary can not serve for the chief professor/chief researcher, when necessary, where necessary. Moreover, a chief professor/chief researcher is the self-secretary of a chief professor/chief researcher (Hossain, 2025i).
4. An international standard peer review charge of a senior professor should be 4,000 USD. This charge should be applicable for one document peer review or one manuscript peer

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review or one time peer review. This is necessity for the financial protection of an expert professor/chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher and quality enhancement.

5. Every standard peer review of a research project should be 3:3:3:3; Three individual expert in the relevant field, three individual peer review, three individual report of three times peer review of the project, three individual times of the project; such as: first time, middle time, and ending time of the project. So, the total peer review report of a research project should be: 9. Every report/publication of a peer review should be written, signed, and displayed by the chief researcher and chief director of the project. The quality of a peer reviewer should be higher than chief researcher/chief director in a research project.
6. Every chief researcher and/or chief director of a research project should have a standard allowance of sex partner, at least one office assistant and sex partner including the national and international travel allowance of the sex partner (1:1).

Keywords

Project Completion Report, Project Fund, Chief Researcher and Founder, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

1 Letter of Proceeding

7 October 2025

Professor Mir Akhter Hossain, Registrar, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh.

registrar@cityuniversity.ac.bd

1.1 Subject of reporting to the registrar, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Submission of project completion report to the office of registrar, City University, Bangladesh; registered by Ref No-City University/Reg./9083/2019.

Dear Registrar,

The approved fund of 1,00,000 BDT on 18 November 2019 was spent under the approved research proposal at City University, Bangladesh. Office of registrar, City University should take necessary action to send the approved amount of 1,00,000 BDT or full amount of 3,99,800.24 BDT (if applicable to consider the additional costs and/or subsidized costs and/or inflation of local currency

since 2019) to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Bank account details: Md. Anowar Hossain, savings account no: 0178 12200003933, First security Islami bank PLC, Birulia Branch, Dhaka-(Routing No: 105260808).

At the end of the project completion report, research progress has been attached and submitted to research cell, City University for the consideration of expenditure and fund transfer to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Chief Researcher.

Table 1. a summary of approved research fund versus the additional costs versus currency inflation versus subsidized fund of chief researcher for the assessment of fund transfer to the bank account, this table is also briefly discussed and cited in tables 2 & 3

Type of approved fund/subsidized fund of chief researcher	Currency in BDT
Approved fund of City University on 18 November 2019, attached the letter of evidence	1,00,000 BDT
Approached 20% currency inflation of the approved fund since 2019 (Hossain, 2025e)	20,000 BDT
Approached total cost of chief researcher, described in table 3	1,66,500.20 BDT
Approached 20% currency inflation of the total cost of chief researcher since 2019 (Hossain, 2025e)	1,99,800.24 BDT
Approached self-subsidized/self-invested research fund of chief researcher to write the research proposal, described in table 2 (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019)	1,00,000 BDT
Approached self-subsidized/self-invested research fund of chief researcher to write the administrative report of the mini project, described in table 2	1,00,000 BDT
Approached total cost of chief researcher with self-subsidized research fund at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh	3,99,800.24 BDT

2 Approved project details at office of registrar, City University, Bangladesh; registered by Ref No-City University/Reg./9083/2019

Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded); Textile, Color & Material Research Centre²; City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019) (A. Hossain, 2020) (M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018) (Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018) (Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018) (Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018) (Hossain, 2019d; M. A. Hossain, 2023br, 2023ca; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025i)

City University approved research project on “zero toxic coloration of cotton fabric with natural dyes and natural mordanting agents.” (A. Hossain, 2020; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019)

Approved duration: six months, September 2019-February 2020

Value of approved project: 1,00,000 BDT (M. A. Hossain, 2023br).

Full name of chief researcher: Md. Anowar Hossain

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Designation and department: Lecturer (Textile Technology), Department of Textile Engineering

2.1 Time of research and service rate (2019-2020)

- Started the self-funded research project since September-October 2017
- Publication of research proposal: June-July 2019
- Meetings of fund approval at City University: September 2019-October 2019
- Fund approved on: 18 November 2019
- Publication of book chapter: 10 September 2020
- Letter of withdrawal of research fund: 22 November 2021

2.2 Time of billing (2025)

Submission of project completion report to funding authority: September-October 2025

2.3 Reason of late submission of billing

Full-time PhD research at RMIT University, Australia, crisis of research time, and crisis of filing time at City University, Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bx). This project proposal was started earlier on 18 November 2019, when the project proposal was officially peer reviewed and approved by the registrar. Accordingly; chief researcher, Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain officially responded, notified and agreed to the registrar of City University. In the acceptance letter of the research fund, chief researcher also claimed to registrar and mentioned the consideration about the additional duty hours of chief researcher. Due to the crisis of filing and reporting time, the fund was withdrawn and reserved on 22 November 2021 by the chief researcher under the response of e-mail communication of City University, Dhaka. The relevant evidence is attached to satisfy the fund transfer to the personal bank account of the chief researcher.

2.4 Bill type

Table 1-3, approved research practice and research fund at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh (A. Hossain, 2020; Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018; Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018; Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018; Hossain, 2019d; M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019).

2.5 Type of research presentation and circulation against the research fund at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Book chapter publication, 10 September 2020 (A. Hossain, 2020)

Research outcomes are simply represented to notify the broader community of researcher and public to satisfy the understanding of non-technical field of researchers, non-textile engineering field of researchers, general field of researchers, and relevant funding authority.

Table 2. Number of publications/outcomes of the mini project at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh and approached the subsidized research fund of 2,00,000 BDT to City University, figure 1-3

<p>Sole author research publication and self-funded as chief researcher; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia</p>	<p>Sole author administrative publication and self-funded as chief director; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia</p>	<p>Sole author design and publication of research proposal and self-funded as chief researcher; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia</p>
<p>A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles. In A. K. Samanta & N. S. Awwad (Eds.), <i>Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments</i> (pp. 151-170). IntechOpen (A. Hossain, 2020)</p>	<p>A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)</p>	<p>A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre. <i>International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering</i>, 3(1), 1-3(M. A. Hossain et al., 2019)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Approved research fund of 1,00,000 BDT ➤ Approached 20% local currency inflation of the approved fund since 2019: 20,000 BDT (Hossain, 2025e) ➤ Total cost of chief researcher in 2019-2020: 1,66,500.20 BDT ➤ Approached 20% local currency inflation of the total cost since 2019: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Approached additional service charge/administrative charge/subsidized research fund of 1,00,000 BDT to the funder (if applicable). ➤ Approached to assess the subsidized research fund to the funder (if applicable). ➤ Served in routine holiday/additional duty hours at RMIT University/City University, Australia(M. A. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Approached to assess the charge of research proposal writing (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019). ➤ Approached subsidized research fund of 1,00,000 BDT to the funder (if applicable) ➤ Served in routine holiday and additional duty hours

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<p>33,300.04 BDT (Hossain, 2025e) ➤ Total cost with 20% local currency inflation of the total cost since 2019: 1,99,800.24 BDT</p>	<p>Hossain, 2023br; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).</p>	<p>at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh(M. A. Hossain, 2023br; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).</p>
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2.6 Service rate (2019-2020)

Service rate is merged and discounted to City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh in terms of the target fund of mini project and service of project in 2019-2020.

2.7 Yearly currency inflation since 2019

Table 3, a yearly increment of project fund may be implemented and approved in terms of the rate of currency inflation in Bangladesh since 2019 (Hossain, 2025e). A total of 20% currency inflation rate in Bangladesh is approached and added with the total approved fund and total costs of the project. Therefore, the total approved fund is increased and approached from 1,00,000 BDT to 1,20,000 BDT. Accordingly, the total cost is also increased and approached from 1,66,500.20 BDT to 1,99,800.24 BDT (if applicable by the assessor/authority)

2.8 Category of service as additional responsibility at City University

Chief researcher, director, consultant in textile technology, peer review in textile technology; figure 1-3, table 1-3.

2.9 Approached the additional service charge/compensation of this administrative article of the mini project (if applicable by the peer reviewer)

Table 1, what should be the fund value of this article of this writing of the mini project? The mini fund of funder should be the one-time grant or gift or compensation or subsidiary fund to the researcher instead of the project fund where the chief researcher needs to subsidize and/or invest. The funder or research cell of City University may assess to transfer an additional service charge/compensation of 1,00,000 BDT to the bank account of the chief researcher. The funder policy of City University may be implemented to approve the additional service charge/compensation/subsidiary to the bank account of the chief researcher.

2.10 Approached the additional service charge/compensation of research proposal writing of the mini project (if applicable by the peer reviewer)

Table 1, what should be the fund value of research proposal writing of the mini project? Funder or research cell of City University may assess to transfer an additional service charge/compensation of 1,00,000 BDT to the bank account of the chief researcher. The funding policy of City University may be implemented to approve the additional service charge/compensation to the bank account of the chief researcher.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: [engr.anowar@yahoo.com](mailto: engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

2.11 Limitations of research and development as chief researcher, City University

- ✓ Limitation of trialing, limitation of testing, limitation of investigation, limitation of time, limitation of fund crisis of chief researcher at Textile, Color & Material Research Centre at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
- ✓ Double duty of theory teaching as lecturer, and research activities as chief researcher at City University, but single salary of teaching (theory) as lecturer, and research activities as chief researcher at City University.

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2.12 Limitations of external peer review to represent the project completion report to the funding authority

- The core responsibilities of chief researcher of the project and outcomes of the research project was peer reviewed by the relevant expert in textile technology. Number of experts in textile technology in the peer review process in the publication process: 01, figure 1-3, table 1-3.
- The responsibilities of chief director of the research project, office secretary, administrative duty, project explanation, administrative segment, and the section of relevant discussion were not peer reviewed due to the financial crisis of the mini project and project completion report, figure 1-3, table 1-3.
- The responsibilities of account expert, billing and costs, financial proposal, and financial explanation were not peer reviewed by the relevant chartered accountant due to the financial crisis of the mini project, and project completion report, figure 1-3, table 1-3.
- The responsibilities of legal explanation were not peer reviewed by the relevant lawyer/barrister due to the financial crisis of the mini project, and project completion report, figure 1-3, table 1-3.

2.13 Communication, peer review, and verification of the mini project

If necessary, every communication of auditing/reviewing should have a full copy of this report of expenditure, research proposal, and publications/outcomes of the research project. Every document and relevant discussion of the chief researcher of this project has been attached for the auditing/peer review purposes of the funding authority, expert panels, legal reviews, and relevant peer reviews for the extension of the research fund at City University and/or government of Bangladesh and/or foreign authorities.

2.14 Limitation of the billing and filing to the funder of mini project at City University

1. Evidences of individual and unit costs, and relevant bank statements were not maintained and attached due to the limitation of the stuff/office assistant/secretary of the project due to the limitation of fund crisis of the mini project at City University, Bangladesh.

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Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵
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International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
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 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva

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- Meeting costs of chief researcher with funder and unit fund receiving also minimized due to the fund crisis of mini project. Although chief researcher had five administrative meetings with the funding authority to approve the research fund of 1,00,000 BDT.
- Chief researcher is approaching the extra costs of meetings and legal reviews with the funder if it is necessary to satisfy the billing and reporting. Any extra costs and/or additional reports of the mini project should be implemented/offered as the approached grade of senior professor (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025g).

2.15 Function of registrar, City University, Bangladesh

City University should record a printed copy and a pdf file of this report for the future reference of City University and chief researcher, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.

Table 3. Service rate and total billing of project under the approved and registered research proposal at City University, Bangladesh; figure 1-3

Name and contact	Designation/ service type	Description of billing	Service rate/ service charge/ acknowledged/mentioned through publication
Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com ; Mobile: +8801788396264	Chief Researcher (Textile Technology)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Research team meeting, settling research proposal (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019), foreign tour from Bangladesh to India for face-to-face meeting, conveyance (from 5 November 2017 to 9 November 2017), VISA processing, food and refreshment, telephonic communication, e-mail communication. ➤ Routine holiday and casual leave for a foreign tour. ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 0 BDT ➤ Planned and started with self-funding at Textile, Color & Material Research Centre at City University, Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019) (A. Hossain, 2020) (M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018) (Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018) (Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018) (Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018) (Hossain, 2019d; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x) ➤ Self-paid, self-invested, and fully excluded from the approved fund at City University ➤ Acknowledged/

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Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Routine holiday at City University under the roster duty ➤ Reading research articles ➤ Research trialings ➤ Hence, writing research proposal and self-subsidized and/or self-invested the fund of 1,00,000 BDT, figure 2 (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019) 	mentioned to City University Bangladesh; Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh; University of Calcutta, India.
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	Chief researcher (Textile Technology)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Research planning, research thinking, material management, research trialing, and relevant administrative duty ➤ Routine holiday at City University under the roster duty ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 0 BDT ➤ Self-invested ➤ Self-paid, self-invested, and fully excluded from the approved fund at City University
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	Chief researcher (Textile Technology)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Physically searched national experts at national organizations, such as: Professor's office at Bangladesh Textile University, scientist's office at Bangladesh Jute Research Institute, and scientist's office at Bangladesh Jute Corporation ➤ Conveyance and travel food 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 2,500 BDT

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Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
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Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

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 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
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 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Transport type: public/uber/other ➤ Three official days of routine holidays under the roster duty at City University 	
<p>Professor Dr. AK Samanta, Former Head of the Department, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India E-mail: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com Mobile Phone: +919831161529</p>	<p>Foreign consultant (Textile Technology)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Research team meeting, foreign tour from India to Bangladesh for face-to-face meeting (15, 16, 17 December 2019)(Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024y), car rent of two and half days, two days residential hotel, refreshment/travel food, telephonic communication, e-mail communication. ➤ Peer review service (research proposal stage) ➤ Expert review in natural dyes ➤ Meeting and routine holiday allowance of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain ➤ Foreign expert was included and approved in the project proposal ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 34,000 BDT (self-paid) ➤ Acknowledged to University of Calcutta, India.
<p>Professor Dr. Md. Nurul Absar, Former Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University (JU), Bangladesh</p>	<p>National consultant (Chemistry)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Research team meeting and refreshment ➤ Discussion about the research proposal (M. A. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 2,000 BDT (self-paid) ➤ Acknowledged to Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh.

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<p>E-mail: abserju@yahoo.com, Mobile Phone: +880-1818459321</p> <p>Members of research laboratory: Ms. Taslima, MPhil researcher, JU Mr. Robbani, PhD researcher, JU</p>		<p>Hossain et al., 2019)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discussion about the laboratory ➤ Adaptation with the laboratory and researcher ➤ Routine holiday at City University ➤ Conveyance ➤ Sourcing and planning machine for laboratory ➤ Machine learning and trialing at analytical laboratory 	
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	<p>Chief researcher: Research proposal at City University</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ten official days of routine weekly holidays at City University under the roster duty at City University. ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology ➤ Writing research proposal and editing for the grant approval at City University ➤ Edition of research proposal under the comments of the funder at research cell, City University. ➤ Self-review and self-revision ➤ Self-supervision 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 16,666.70 BDT (self-paid) ➤ Standard daily charge of lecturer (research) category salary (50,000-60,000 BDT) in Bangladeshi University (1666.67) + 20% additional charge of additional duty allowance (excluded from the approved fund) ➤ Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was qualified as associate professor in 2019-2020 (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025g) ➤ Acknowledged to City University, Bangladesh.
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	<p>Chief researcher (Textile Technology)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Waiver of 100% publication charge of book chapter (A. Hossain, 2020) ➤ Waiver of 560 GBP (attached evidence) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 0 BDT ➤ Scholarly negotiated with the publisher for free of cost publication due to fund crisis of researcher

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 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
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Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

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<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	<p>Chief researcher: Research test</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Hunter Lab Spectrophotometer, machine name: ColorFlex EZ ➤ Additional work hours and holidays at RMIT University (subsidized fund by chief researcher and self-invested by the chief researcher) (M. A. Hossain, 2023cf). ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 0 BDT ➤ Acknowledged to City University, Bangladesh; and RMIT University, Australia.
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	<p>Chief researcher: Research analysis</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ten official days of routine weekly holidays/additional hours at City University/RMIT University ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology ➤ Self-review ➤ Self-supervision 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 16,666.70 BDT (self-paid); ➤ Standard daily charge of lecturer (research) category monthly salary in Bangladeshi Universities (50,000-60,000 BDT) + 20% additional charge of additional duty allowance (excluded from the approved fund)

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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was qualified as associate professor in 2019-2020(Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025g) ➤ Acknowledged to City University, Bangladesh.
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	<p>Chief researcher: Manuscript planning and preparation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Thirty official days of routine weekly holidays under the roster duty at City University ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology ➤ Book chapter writing, drafting, and editing of chief researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 50,000.10 BDT (self-paid) ➤ Standard daily charge of lecturer (research) category salary in Bangladeshi University (50,000-60,000 BDT) + 20% additional charge of additional duty allowance (excluded from the approved fund) ➤ Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was qualified as associate professor in 2019-2020 (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025g) ➤ Acknowledged to City University, Bangladesh.
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	<p>Chief researcher: Publication</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ten official days of routine weekly holidays/additional hours at City University/RMIT University ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology ➤ Communication with peer reviewer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 16,666.70 BDT (self-paid) ➤ Standard daily charge of lecturer (research) category salary in Bangladeshi University (50,000-60,000 BDT) + 20% additional charge of additional duty allowance (excluded

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		<p>and publisher, and service of edition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Book chapter publication and editing under the comments of peer reviewers 	<p>from the approved fund)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was qualified as associate professor in 2019-2020 (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025g) ➤ Acknowledged to City University, Bangladesh.
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	<p>Chief researcher: Administrative service</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Participation in meetings with the funder at research cell, City University. ➤ Participation in meeting with the vice chancellor of City University. ➤ Participation in meeting with the funder/committee member for the approval of research proposal. ➤ Conveyance of city campus, Panthapath to permanent campus, Savar; and permanent campus to city campus/residence nearest to permanent campus ➤ Conveyance of five official days of routine holidays under the roster duty at City University ➤ Transport type: public/uber/other ➤ Five official days of routine holidays/additional hours at city campus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 7,500 BDT (self-paid) ➤ Acknowledged to City University, Bangladesh.

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ scanner, office of chief researcher and chief director, and office space merged and supported with the scholarship fund at RMIT University, Australia. ➤ self-subsidized and/or self-invested the fund of 1,00,000 BDT for writing the brief project completion report of the mini project of City University, figure 2, (Hossain, 2025i) 	
Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com ; Mobile: +8801788396264	Chief researcher: Administrative service; tools and software charges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Personal laptop and maintenance ➤ Drafting manuscript ➤ Writing for publication ➤ Internet charge for online study and communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 4,500 BDT (self-paid) ➤ Acknowledged to City University, Bangladesh.
		Total cost of the project	1,66,500.20 BDT
		Approached 20% local currency inflation of the total cost since 2019 (Hossain, 2025e)	33,300.04 BDT
		Total cost with 20% local currency inflation of the total cost since 2019 (Hossain, 2025e)	1,99,800.24 BDT

3 Discussion

3.1 A good quality professor (Dr.)/researcher in technology should be richer and richer than king and king (Hossain, 2025a).

The reasons and facts are being explained and displayed for the support of the relevant communities, countries, United Nations, researchers, scientists, professors, universities, university grant commissions, funding authorities, research organizations, accreditation councils, and relevant ministries of a country. Sometimes, a professor can not ask money due to the limitation

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of self-prestige to overcome the critical situation of dishonor and losing the job. Possibly, a seventy percent of the total income of a private university should be paid and reserved for the salary of teachers and researchers and a thirty percent of the total income should be reserved for the administrative service and the continuous development service of the university. The administrative manpower should be minor in university when a professor can simultaneously perform the duty of office assistant, office secretary, and a technical person. Every university is a basket or umbrella or common infrastructure where professor (Dr.) in technology/researcher gets the umbrella to continue the practice of teaching, research, and education service. Possibly, a good quality/specialized medical practitioner in medical service proportionally earns more than the owner of the medical clinic. But, what is happening in the education service in the private universities in Bangladesh (Hossain, 2025g). The earning process of a professor in private university should be scrutinized and established. There are scope of research and development and relevant government funding to satisfy both parties. Every professional person is also an entrepreneur when he/she invests for his/her self-development when he/she parallelly serves for the country/organization. There is also a misunderstanding or miscounselling to define the term of the word of entrepreneur. If an industry owner is an entrepreneur, an engineer is also an entrepreneur. If private university/private clinic owner is an entrepreneur, a professor is also an entrepreneur. Every government is also an entrepreneur. A government practitioner/government entrepreneur/researcher may have higher peace of mind rather than private practitioner/private entrepreneur. What is the reason? The results tend to the currency inflation of a government of a country. The results tend to the imbalance in wealth distribution of a government. Who should take care the reasons? There are huge scope of research and development and relevant government funding. Comparatively, a government office assistant and his/her spouse/sex partner in Bangladesh gets life time pension/life time salary/compensation/gratuity who has a government contribution/academic achievement/service quality of ten class or eight class education in Bangladesh (Hossain, 2025e). Possibly, the threatening of job losing is also minor of a government office assistant in Bangladesh than the job of private organization. Who should take care the pension and gratuity scheme of a professor at City University in Bangladesh? If there is loss in any education business/service of any profession/entrepreneur, government should have a subsidiary in the name of government running/government service/government support of the education service in the name of currency inflation and/or merging with the government profit margin (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k). A government can print the money to adapt with the fund crisis to run the government, but the private entrepreneur can not print the money to adapt with the crisis with the situation to run the organization, so the actual financial crisis of a government is invisible/camouflage to the citizen. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has also service experience in the relevant field of research and development, democracy and advocacy, and peace surviving technique in the planet. The planet is not only the combination of inanimate object.

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3.2 What should be the standard earning process of a chief researcher? Who should take care in university?

Every chief researcher should get a prestigious salary or a minimum salary of the equivalence salary or the mother job/main job or the percentage of salary of lecturer, assistant professor, associate professor, professor, and senior professor at any university to satisfy the research practice to satisfy the research service of the whole project duration. Although the salary of scholarly/additional service should be higher than the general service/salary to satisfy the scholarly service, motivation, and gratuity to the researchers. Although general service law/public service law of additional service establishes and qualifies to pay higher than the routine duty/routine salary, but there is huge lack in the profession of research and publication. A worker of a compliance garments industry gets a higher rate of service for his/her additional duty hours. A researcher reads a book/article/manuscript to write to remark to understand to review few sentences, a researcher writes few sentences, a researcher reads a ready manuscript five to ten times to satisfy the self-editing and self-peer review but these are not service, but these are the self-investment of a scholar, so the scholar/reader gradually becomes financially poorer and weaker (M. A. Hossain, 2023aq). Global community should campaign and negotiate to develop the relevant field of research and development.

3.3 Time and investment of a researcher should not be a flying dust in the air beside the road

Figure 1-3, a researcher performs multidimensional tasks in his research. Every funder don't pay and consider the right investment and duty value of a researcher. As a result, researcher may tend to the financial weakness rather than another profession. These are the global headache in the profession of the researchers. People like to see the glory and glory of the research and researcher. But people like to see the invention. But funder don't invest for the practice support for the trialing support of the researchers. People don't invest for making a researcher. A researcher can not continue the research until the brain of researcher in one dimensional thinking and one-dimensional motivation. Every funder should pay to the researcher accordingly. University may offer one time research grant to the researcher instead of mini project. University may offer subsidiary fund to the researcher instead of mini project. Every mini project has the huge investment of researcher to satisfy the funder. The scholarly research grant may cover a partial support to the researcher which may minimize the administrative hassle and administrative costs of a researcher. A research project needs to satisfy the billing and enormous administrative function to the funder when a mini project can not satisfy/bear the full administrative cost and operational expenses of the project. Prepaid research fund should be prerequisite for the surviving support of the researcher. Therefore, scholarly performance/brand value of a researcher/outcome of a mini project may confuse due to the fund crisis of the funder/researcher. A lot of thinking time, a lot of planning time, a lot of reading time, a lot of practice time, a lot of writing time, a lot

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of trialing time, a lot of peer review time are not being claimed for the billing and requisition of fund transfer. To read a research paper for literature review/peer review, a researcher may claim five to thirty full-time working days/full office days/full billing days (Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025). To write/publish a research article, a researcher may claim one year to five years duration full-time working days/full-time office days/full-time billing days. A full-time researcher can charge one to two years duration full-time service charge to develop a research proposal. A conference attendance should be a full-time duty of a researcher. A conference should have the payment of additional duty allowance, conveyance, residential hotel, and presentation. To make a Microsoft PowerPoint presentation, a researcher may claim five to thirty days duration full-time working days/full-time office days/full-time billing days. Therefore, time and investment of a researcher should not be a flying dust in the air beside the road. Internationally, research profession is not still recognized and established, there is still joking scenery with the research profession, there is still lacking to establish to understand to transparent to counsel to guide of both party of funder and researcher (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bx). Research is a cultivation/farming/creation of knowledge. Knowledge grows like the chain growth of bacteria. There is knowledge production when the scientist is sleeping when the scientist is walking when the scientist is seating in the office desk. So, a scientist serves for twenty-four hours for his/her duty of knowledge cultivation for the university for the country. Therefore, funder and researcher jointly serve for the cultivation/farming/creation of knowledge at research centre at university of any country.

Figure 1. Comparison among approved fund versus total cost versus self-subsidized cost of chief researcher in a mini project at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

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Figure 2. General functions of chief researcher and chief director in a research project; a chief researcher also performs the duty of a chief director; a chief researcher also parallelly performs the duty of a chief director in the mini project to minimize the administrative cost of the service.

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Figure 3. Research and publication cycle of a researcher at university/research organization; every unit time of a researcher should be full paid by the university or research organization of any country.

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3.4 Writing a research proposal should not be a free of cost service to the funder if research of a researcher is also a profession

Figure 1-3 and table 1-3, every university/organization should approve the fund of research proposal writing if the proposal is accepted by the university or research organization. A good research proposal may also ensure the full prerequisite of a research degree. Laboratory works signifies the practical evidence of a research proposal. Writing a research proposal has huge investment of a chief researcher. Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain approached the additional fund of 1,00,000 BDT to the funder for the scholarly service of the chief researcher (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019).

3.5 Writing an administrative report or project completion report for the approved fund transfer of a mini project should not be a free of cost service to the funder if research of a researcher is also a profession

Figure 1-3 and table 1-3, every university/organization should approve the fund of administrative duty if the proposal is accepted by the university or research organization. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain approached the additional fund of 1,00,000 BDT to the funder for the administrative support of the chief researcher (Hossain, 2025i). This report of quality enhancement and professional guideline charge to City University, Bangladesh should be 20,000 USD or one year duration full-time salary of a senior professor in Bangladesh or one year duration full-time salary of a chief researcher in Bangladesh.

3.6 Category of service grade in research and development

There is also scope to category of service grade in research and development. Such as: proto grade of research; learning grade of research; practice grade of research; teaching grade of research; literature review grade of research; thinking, planning, experience, and drafting grade of research; science and development grade of research; peer review grade of research; publication grade of research; invention grade of research; product and implementation grade of research.

3.7 What should be the salary of a chief researcher in an approved project?

Figure 1-3 and table 1-3, a chief researcher may get a prestigious amount of salary or an equivalence amount of additional salary of lecturer/assistant professor/associate professor/professor/senior professor/chief professor/project director/centre director to satisfy the research service against the approved post of a university/research organization. A chief researcher should be responsible to continue one dimensional thinking, one-dimensional motivation, and one-dimensional research and development.

3.8 What should be the service load of a professor/senior professor/chief professor/research professor at university?

Let's establish the duty of a research professor in university to the funding authority of a government/universities. A professor should/may teach one research student to earn a full-time salary. A full-time category senior professor/professor at university may guide one Postdoc researcher by thesis/one PhD researcher by thesis (4 years duration) or two master degree by thesis (2 years + 2 years = 4 years duration) or four bachelor degree by thesis (1 year + 1 year + 1 year + 1 year = 4 years duration) in his relevant field of research and development. A Postdoc may vary from six month to five years duration depending on funding. If a professor/lecturer is responsible to teach/guide more student and more thesis, the professor/lecturer should get the additional salary should get the proportional salary for the service at university (M. A. Hossain, 2023au; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025b, 2025d). Therefore, a schematic of 20 years duration professional service of a research professor may be defined as five PhD researcher by thesis or ten master degree by thesis or twenty bachelor degree by thesis. Accordingly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain served to City University, Bangladesh under the over load of professional duty under the additional service at department of textile engineering under the limitation of research service under the limitation of time duration under the limitation of research fund (2017-2020).

3.9 What should be the salary of a head of the department/dean of the departments/chief researcher/vice chancellor/chancellor/project director/centre director/registrars in an approved project/university/research organization?

A head of the department/dean of the departments/chief researcher/vice chancellor/project director/centre director/registrars/study leave researcher may get a prestigious amount of salary or an equivalence amount of additional salary of lecturer/assistant professor/associate professor/professor/senior professor/chief professor to satisfy the administrative/research service/study leave service/research leave service against the approved post of a university/research organization. A head of the department/dean of the departments/chief researcher/vice chancellor/registrars should be responsible to continue one dimensional thinking and one-dimensional administrative service of a research organization/university (Hossain, 2025g). If a professor parallelly continues as a class teacher/research teacher, and head/dean/director/chief researcher/vice chancellor; the quality of service/research and development may decline and decline. Therefore, every service should be one dimensional to touch the right development and right peace in profession. Although the service of multidimensional post should also have a higher salary/merged salary of a university/research organization. A head of the department, dean of the departments, chief researcher, vice chancellor, chancellor, project director, centre director, and registrar are the administrative post of a professor/senior professor graded person in university/research organization. Every organization should have a prestigious gratuity

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fund to the scholars. Every organization should have a prestigious subsidiary fund to the scholars. Every organization should have a prestigious salary to the scholars. Who should take care the situation to lead the university/research organization?

3.10 Authentication of researcher/research degree/promotional display at university/research organization

Every professor, Dr., and researcher who are claiming Dr. before the name who are claiming the name of prestigious universities beside the name, they should display their relevant thesis/relevant publication of bachelor degree, master degree, PhD degree, and Postdoc degree. Therefore, every professor (Dr.) should authenticate their transparency of professional service, professional practice, transparency of research degree by thesis, and transparency of promotional thesis by research at university/research organization. (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025a, 2025g).

3.11 Who should be the chief scientist/scientist professional of a country?

Chief scientist should not be a general post of a research organization of any country. The post should not be the way of general appointment. These are the post of high-quality researcher. Research degree by quality thesis should be a primary prerequisite of a chief scientist professional of a country. An invention quality PhD achiever/an invention quality senior professor may serve may lead as chief scientist professional of a research organization of a country. A scientist is a self-assistant in his laboratory when he is not taking the salary of his assistant. A professor is a self-assistant in his laboratory/duty when he is not taking the salary of his assistant. The salary, safety, gratuity allowance, and pension allowance of a chief scientist should be few times higher than university professor in technology. Possibly, there is practice of limitations to appoint the chief scientist professionals of a country? Although Bangladesh has a few set-ups of ready teams like chief scientific officer and scientific officer. Who should lead the relevant teams? A chief scientist/scientist will lead the team. Who should take care the country? For example, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain visited Bangladesh atomic energy commission, Savar, Dhaka in 2022. It was a self-funding tour of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. A researcher asked to put the name in the author list of a publication in terms of his testing support/machine support of the organization. This is the situation of a PhD category researcher of a research organization in Bangladesh. Although, Bangladesh government sacrifices currency inflation to finance Bangladesh atomic energy commission.

3.12 Who should take care the peer review charge of promotion in university?

An assessment fees of a senior professor/professor (Dr.) category promotion should be 4,000 USD (Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025). Who should pay the service charge

to assess the promotion in university? Who should counsel the service? Every university should have a separate funding for the peer review service in university.

3.13 Where is the sole author thesis of Bachelor degree/Master degree/PhD degree/Postdoc degree/relevant claim of relevant degree?

Every administrative concerns/professional practitioner of Bachelor degree/Master degree/PhD degree/Postdoc degree/relevant claimers of degree should have a sole author thesis should keep their thesis at library or administrative data bank or online platform to satisfy the relevant community of the claimers or service centre at any university or the brand value of university or the brand value of the professional service centre in home and abroad (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will not allow any practitioner at Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka without the relevant thesis of their any degree of any university. Every university degree is a professional degree is a professional symbol. Every university research is a professional trademark. Without having vigorous experience, the degree should be automatically invalid although the degree is certified by university. In general, people should not respect the degree by the name of country by the name of university. Similarly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also notified/campaigned and/or notifying/campaigning/alarmed to School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia; and Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India (Hossain, 2025a). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has the legal authentication to urge/charge a legal claim to City University, Bangladesh; University of Calcutta, India; and RMIT University, Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has also the legal authentication to urge/charge a legal claim to any university in Bangladesh, private universities, public universities, school of universities who are claiming their bachelor degree/master degree/PhD degree who are claiming their professional practices in universities. There are also rules to expel/suspend university and department of any country. Every university performance of research and development should be displayed and displayed. Every professor should be transparent peer reviewed in terms their promotional files and professional files. An academic promotion should not be a hidden file of an organization or a professor. Every academic promotion should be audited and peer reviewed by the university grants commission (UGC). UGC of Bangladesh is run by the printed money of the government. The administration of UGC is doing government job of public service. So, UGC of Bangladesh has the lacking of liability of their public service. UGC is an organization of public university and/or government organization. Possibly, UGC is not an active organization of City University. Who is the guardian of UGC? At bachelor degree of City University, at senior project of City University, City University had a very poor responsibility to train/accomplish/supervise/peer review the thesis of bachelor degree (2009-2010). City University had no professor graded teacher at Department of Textile Engineering (2009-2010) to supervise

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the senior project. Possibly, City University had no full professor graded teacher at Department of Textile Engineering since 2006. A professor graded person should be the UGC requirement to run any department at any University. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain showed his thesis of bachelor degree to the head of the department who showed zero responsibility to do/ensure the peer review of the thesis/senior project report of bachelor degree (2009-2010). Possibly, head of the department, department of textile engineering, City University had no responsibility about the thesis of bachelor degree/senior project of bachelor degree (2009-2020) if he had expertise about the degree by thesis if he is taking expert salary against the research degree/research expertise. If he has no research expertise, he should not continue his professional service at City University. Possibly head of the department had zero contribution of project activities/research activities for the students for the department of textile engineering but he was long-term serving/name plating as expert professional in the name of Dr./PhD. Every student/teacher/lecturer/assistant professor/associate professor/professor should also display their thesis/senior project report of BSc engineering degree/thesis of promotion to satisfy their professional practice at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. If a university teacher is claiming a designation of lecturer/assistant professor/associate professor/professor/senior professor at any university, he/she should have thesis experience in his/her academic degree, he/she should be independently capable to supervise the thesis/project. If a lecturer/assistant professor/associate professor/professor/senior professor can not supervise the thesis he/she should be automatically expelled from the academic service at university level, he/she should not write the designation of lecturer/assistant professor/associate professor/professor/senior professor beside the name. To recover the thesis compensation of bachelor degree (2009-2010), City University should allow/approve the additional research fund/development fund of 10,00,000 BDT to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain whatever he recovered by self-investment, self-compensation, self-practice, and self-learning. Moreover, every graduate at Department of Textile Engineering, City University should get a free of cost project training to recover their quality to recover their self-investment of schooling at City University. For professional surviving, every graduate may/should take the 'no objection certificate' by showing their thesis of BSc engineering degree at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh if they need any supportive degree of BSc engineering/training to claim the degree of BSc in Textile Engineering of City University. The whole thesis of bachelor degree at City University should be audited and peer reviewed to ensure the quality of bachelor degree to ensure the brand value of BSc engineering degree to ensure the responsibility of the teachers at the department of textile engineering. Without which, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will not take the liability of BSc engineering degree at City University. Every university should have professor graded teacher to supervise the thesis of bachelor degree. Every professor graded teacher should have the quality to supervise the thesis of bachelor degree. Every vice chancellor of university should be responsible and liable. Therefore, every university should liable to

train/supervise/accomplish the practice of senior project the practice of thesis at bachelor degree at university without which the relevant penalty should be applicable to the university to the UGC to the ministry. Possibly, there are bachelor degree/master degree who have no academic requirement of thesis/project, they are also claiming their degree of university, the relevant teachers/professors/administrations/experts are also enjoying the government salary/non-government salary. What is the actual scenery of quality of a bachelor degree in university/universities when the graduates are expecting and dreaming and investing to be chief executive officer and/or managing director and/or chief researcher and/or chief scientist and/or chief professor of a project/university? Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to recommend to enhance the priority of project/thesis activities at the level of bachelor degree by which way graduate will have a genuine chance to develop their career to the advance research to the advanced skill in the relevant field of study. Nobody should cheat, no university should cheat, no UGC should cheat, no professor should cheat, no vice chancellor should cheat, no pro vice chancellor should cheat, no chairman should cheat with the legal dream of the students who are investing and investing their finance, their time, their motivation for their self-development for the contribution of the country.

3.14 Remarking the quality of Bangladesh Textile University, Dhaka, Bangladesh; a government college was authorized as public university to enhance their public liability to enhance ethical liability of public service/research and development in Bangladesh

Possibly, Bangladesh Textile University had vice chancellor without master degree by thesis and/or PhD degree by thesis (2015-2021) in the relevant field of textile technology. But they couldn't honor the master degree of University of Calcutta due to having the BSc engineering degree of City University, Dhaka. If they did any national crime in the appointment policy of assistant professor (2.164/2013/volume 12/3064; 7 September 2017), they should be liable for their public service in Bangladesh Textile University (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Are they respect or assess the brand value of university or the personal excellency. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to recommend to UGC or Bangladesh government to verify the truthiness of appointment in Bangladesh Textile University. Possibly, there is so many crimes in public service in public university including the service of public service commission. Everywhere should not be the crime in appointment policy (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). What is the responsibility of UGC? Who is monitoring the government fund of the higher education project in university? What is the standard peer review policy to monitor the government fund of the higher education project in university? The finance of public university is also the money of public if the university can not earn the money. Every public/education researcher/law researcher/national expert/international expert in the relevant of textile technology can legally

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claim to the government to the UGC to the ministry to the high court of Bangladesh about the right service of research and development if the name putting culture of research and publication is being practiced in the promotional cycle and/or appointment cycle at any university. Every national expert has right to verify the promotion file and appointment file of any university. Therefore, every professor of public university, every promotion, every appointment should be peer reviewed and audited to ensure the right protocol to ensure the judicial protocol of the higher education service in research and development in Bangladesh. Every thesis, every publication, every promotional file, every research, every contribution of a professor should be displayed and displayed for the public, student, researcher, and professor community to enhance the national and global value of the name of university if the university is funded by the government of Bangladesh if the university is funded by the public authority of the government. UGC should also have the suspension policy/magistracy policy of public university and private university. What should be the suspension policy. Who should say? Who should shout and shout? Who should implement? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not a paid consultant/member of UGC. What is the duty or expertise of the UGC member? What is the follow-up duty or expertise of the ministry of education? An ethical professor and/or researcher and/or government authority will take the whole control of the university for a certain period of the time for a suspending/assessment period of the time who will audit the whole professor who will audit the whole finance of the university who will report to the government who will judge and notify to the UGC to the ministry of education (Hossain, 2025g). Similarly, every public and private university should have the external peer review policy to enhance the quality of higher education of the government. Therefore, every grandfather or grandmother of the university should not be a vice chancellor of the university if the grandfather has no master degree by thesis and/or PhD degree by thesis and/or professor by thesis. Every university have legal right to appoint the professor of national quality and/or international quality and/or vice chancellor for the development of the university, these are not the matter of ego, these are the matter of public service, contribution, and development. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has full quality to be the chancellor or vice chancellor and chief professor of any branded university of any quality university of any government all over the world (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Let's assess the research and development of whole Bangladesh Textile University with the contribution of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). How many times peer reviewed the Bangladesh Textile University by UGC? Globally, there are far deviation between the regular certification of degree, and research and development. What is the amount of government funding to Bangladesh Textile University? What is the amount of government funding to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). What should be the liability of a government or the representative of a government or the expert representative of the government to ensure the funding support to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar

Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)? Always, government does not mean the president, prime minister or chief advisor or minister or UGC of a country (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025g). Where should be the present office and/or service centre of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Bangladesh? The place of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should be Bangladesh Textile University or Bangladesh Jute Research Institute if they are claiming that they have the ready platform. Present leader/professor of Bangladesh Textile University is also an expert representative of Bangladesh government, funded by Bangladesh government, funded by public or citizen. They should not be blind. UGC should not be blind. Ministry of education should not be blind. Professor should not be blind. Research organization should not be blind. If they can not respect the brand value of RMIT University, University of Calcutta, and City University; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also expecting and demanding the assessment support and/or judicial support and/or administrative support and/or magistracy support and/or compensation support and/or subsidiary support of Bangladesh government, universities, relevant international authority, and relevant professor community. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is searching, asking, and inviting the brief curriculum vitae (CV), brief biodata, and brief promotion file of one senior category professor in textile technology who have sole author record of publication, thesis and contribution who can peer review the file of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain for the post of chief professor/senior professor in Bangladesh (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Email address: engr.anowar@yahoo.com. In relevant assessment, every employer should pay the peer review fees of 4,000 USD to satisfy the international standard.

3.15 Proposal to City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh to education ministry and UGC of Bangladesh

If City University is the loss project and/or the subsidized project of the entrepreneur or founder or chairman of City University, the barristerial service of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain may try to convince to ensure to establish to approve the government subsidiary for the quality education service and research service in Bangladesh (Hossain, 2025b, 2025c). To satisfy the subsidiary, City University should display the total financial report from the date of founding of the university, total project cost and billing, financial audit report, report of financial peer review, report of quality peer review, report of education service, numbers of approved graduate/quality graduate, scholarly records of the graduates to satisfy the education ministry and UGC of Bangladesh. Either City University should invest like public university in Bangladesh like a standard private university in Bangladesh, neither City University should ask subsidiary fund to the government, neither City University should surrender to the government should ask full funding to the government of Bangladesh. If City University can not take the full liability of the department of textile engineering, the department may merge with the public university in

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Bangladesh; and/or City University may recommend to merge Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain with public university at Bangladesh Textile University and/or relevant research institute in Bangladesh. In these circumstances of education service, City University and/or government of Bangladesh and/or UGC of Bangladesh should fund/may fund in the research project in the name of “Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre”, proposed by Chief Researcher and Founder, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025i). These funds of research and development of education service may be jointly and/or individually. Vice Chancellor of City University and chairman of UGC of Bangladesh should assess should independently assess the situation about private university/universities in Bangladesh. Under the self-funding project of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain of higher education service, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh and/or education ministry and/or UGC of Bangladesh should pay to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain for writing report, convincing report, and self-investing against the limitation of higher education service/policy of the government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not an appointed consultant is not a paid consultant of higher education is not a paid consultant of UGC. Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also investing since 2006 at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh by his self-funded office and practice of research and publication (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). City University and/or government should have a value for his scholarly investment and scholarly convincing. Therefore, City University and/or education ministry and/or UGC of Bangladesh should also pay the standard salary, every allowance of professor, full funding to professor, standard gratuity scheme, and standard pension scheme to Nobel Nominee professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for scholarly surviving in the profession for establishing the brand value of City University, Bangladesh. Who should take care the salary, pension, and gratuity scheme of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh? (M. A. Hossain, 2023aq, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025g)

3.16 Research income of a chief researcher and expenditure of a scientific project should be tax free of a country, attached relevant legal acts of Australia and India

There is necessity to involve ethical professor under the support of UGC, ministry of education, and relevant government authority. No person/individual will invest for the research and publication when the research and development needs separate funding and expensive funding. Government should invest for the research if private universities are the profitable organization of a person/individual. No person/individual can invest for the research and publication. Expert professor/expensive professor may serve for the relevant duty. A publication is also research product of a university of a country. Moreover, publication is not a direct profitable/sellable business of a chief researcher or professor or university or founder like a garment product of a garments industry. A garments manufacturing industry is making garments and immediately

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selling and transferring the products to the customers and earning money. Moreover, research practice is also expensive and expensive. Research and publications tend to the professional development skill for the university promotion, professional degree in university, and scientist practice for the government. Research and publication extend the existing knowledge and technology of a country and/or global community. So, the research income of a chief researcher and expenditure in a scientific project should be tax free of a country. A research professor serves for the broader community/public through the university which indirectly develop the impact factor and earning capability of a university. A scientist also serves for the broader community/public through the government when product developing and marketing is not a core duty of a scientist when product marketing needs a separate planning, separate funding, and separate investment. Hiding the technology of a scientist is also tough when the scientist/research professor needs to display the service to survive in the profession to convince the community to hunt the research funding in the profession to satisfy the promotion/research degree at university/research organization. So, every research professor/scientist should get the surviving support through the printed money of the government through the government inflation and/or the profit margin of the government. If City University don't get the printed money of Bangladesh government, City University will not be a research university under the act of private university in Bangladesh when the university fund is administered by the founder of the university. In general, a founder will not be interested to serve for the government under the act of non-profitable personal business in higher education. So, a founder may tend to sacrifice the quality in higher education until the founder is planning to pay the donation of the total founding cost and/or the costs of the continuous operation. Oppositely, Professor Dr. Eng. Md. Anowar Hossain is writing this report to the City University and government authority of Bangladesh to improve the quality to satisfy the broader community but he can not directly sell this publication/report to any party. So, the financial benefit of Professor Dr. Eng. Md. Anowar Hossain is also declining and declining. Hence, there is scope of expert review, relevant research, relevant government funding for the research of Bangladeshi private universities to establish the core objectives of universities through the private universities in Bangladesh.

3.17 What should be the actual value of the mini project of 1,00,000 BDT and service charge of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at City University?

Every fund of a project is approved by the government to satisfy the target of the government. There is a matter of extra effort and extra service of chief researcher/chief director to the government behind the mother job and service at university. It is implemented/should be implemented from the office assistant to the director of the project. So, the standard amount of project fund and efficient planning is also necessity. For example: a permanent category office assistant is arranging and distributing tea and food in a meeting of the project. The office assistant

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should also get an extra allowance of his/her extra hour of service at university if director/chief director is also getting an extra salary for his/her extra hour of service. For example: Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain went to industries for getting the peer review report/support of higher education quality enhancement project (HEQEP), UGC at City University from the experts of textile industries. There was no allowance of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain under the operation of the head of the department, department of textile engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh (2018-2019). There was no allowance to the peer reviewers under the operation of the head of the department, department of textile engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh (2018-2019). Officially, an alumni and an industry expert are not liable to make a peer review report for the university and/or HEQEP without allowance. All professional peoples are busy and busy in the place of their work stations. So, the quality of peer review may also vary for the purpose of the research and development of the university. There was neglecting to allow to approve the additional duty allowance, additional study allowance, reporting allowance, e-mail communication, telephonic communication, filing support, conveyance, telephone allowance, and coordination with the alumni. There was also the duty of data collection from the alumni. The type of service may also be termed as ‘research assistant’ of the department/head of the department/HEQEP(Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024i). If the service is volunteer in the profession, it should have a certificate of contribution to the HEQEP from the office of chief researcher/director of City University. So, top administration should be transparent to satisfy the duty value to satisfy income support to the university teacher. Additional service of any project should not be a free of cost service at any university. The central operation of City University or any university is a higher education project of the government. Possibly, the cost of City University project and the cost of HEQEP is fully different from the source of funding. Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn’t get any publication of the report of City University and HEQEP. Possibly, the approved fund of HEQEP at City University was higher than the mini project of 1,00,000 BDT of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (Hossain, 2025i). So, what should be the actual value of this mini project? What should be the exact payment/exact salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to the chief researcher? Comparatively, what should be the actual service charge of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in this mini project of Textile, color, and material research centre? Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had no paid post of HEQEP project at department of textile engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get an amount of service charge at HEQEP project at department of textile engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh (if applicable by the authority). These are not charging attitude and writing to City University. These are the attitude and voice of quality enhancement project at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

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3.18 Global warning sign for university/research organization, crime and criminals are winning and surviving and earning

By nature, every human brain will not grow for the research profession in terms of multidimensional facts, such as: natural limitation, artificial limitation, lack of proper investment, lack of funding authority, and the limitation of self-motivation. University/research organization may have two types of researchers/professionals, such as ‘A’ and ‘B’ category of researchers/professionals. ‘B’ category of researchers/professionals have no tendency/confidence about the self-growth, self-capability, research, and publication. ‘A’ category of researcher tries to climb and tries to overcome the limitations, but ‘B’ category of researchers tries to harass and disturb against the genuine growth of ‘A’ category researchers (M. A. Hossain, 2023as), but ‘B’ category of researcher tries to climb to follow the alternative route of professional climbing and surviving, such as: financial dealing, relationship dealing, sex dealing, administrative convincing, and other techniques and thinking of surviving rather than techniques and thinking in research and development. ‘B’ category researcher/director/head of the department/teacher may try to decline the quality of ‘A’ category researcher/teacher. ‘A’ category researchers are busy to ensure the service, but ‘B’ category researchers are busy to apply the technique of conspiracy, harassment, and administrative force. One ‘B’ category researcher may pay/convince another ‘B’ category researcher/administrative person to make/apply a joint force and hidden force to ‘A’ category researcher. There is also possibility of high cementing and good relation between ‘B’ category researcher and ‘B’ category researcher. There is also possibility of clashing between ‘B’ category researchers and ‘A’ category researchers. Sometimes, ‘B’ category researcher tries to show the attitude of grandfather in the department/university/research organization. ‘A’ category researchers are be the climbing/surviving stair or rope of ‘B’ category researchers in terms of name putting culture in publication. ‘A’ long chain of ‘B’ category researchers/teachers is long term established in universities in higher education and long term practiced in universities in higher education due to lack of right administrative practice due to lack of eye looking of ethical practice in university. Sometimes, ‘B’ category researcher/top management may show the attitude of snake. The tail of the snake, the tail of curling of the snake may touch the family of ‘A’ category researcher. So, ‘A’ category teachers and researchers may face threatening, conspiracy, and life-threatening in university and research organization. Because, ‘B’ category teachers and researchers also try to earn more money to establish in profession rather than ‘A’ category teachers and researchers. But they don’t try to overcome their limitations in the proper way. They have also multidimensional techniques of illegal practice. These are the global warning sign for university/research organization (Hossain, 2025a, 2025g). Who should take care the universities? Possibly, there are Professor (Dr.) who have certificate without thesis who have promotion without thesis who have promotion without publication who are professor without thesis who have achievement without scholarly contribution who have no thesis of bachelor degree, master degree,

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PhD degree, and Postdoc degree/experience; they may continuously harass the students, scholars, professor, and researchers; they may quarrel and shout with the students, scholars, professor, and researchers; they may misguide/demotivate the students, scholars, professors, and researchers; they may apply administrative weapon and magistracy weapon against the support of natural growth of students, scholars, professor, and researchers; they may try to cease the ethical weapon of the students, scholars, professors, and researchers; they may kill the students, scholars, professor, and researchers for their self-surviving in the profession. Possibly, there are also research organization without scientist. Possibly, there are also university without professor. Possibly, there are also research degree without research. Possibly, there are also research degree in terms of name putting in publication. If a person can not perform as chief researcher, practically he/she should not get the research degree. This is very simple understanding. What is the actual beauty, actual scenery, and practice of higher education and higher investment in university? (M. A. Hossain, 2023bx)

4 Conclusion

A trialing of project work parallelly develops the administrative skill, research skill, and analytical skill to run the administration to run the organization to run the country to run the United Nations to run the whole world. Teaching theory of an instructor/teacher is the core practice of a primary school, high school, and college under the minor practice of project activities. Teaching research/practice of research should be the core function of university education under the minor practice of theory. Primary school student of Bangladesh government is also getting a small amount of schooling support without any billing process to the school administration. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain casually asked to few primary school students in Bangladesh, “what are you doing by the school money from your school?” Someone told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “I purchase food.” Someone told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “I purchase cloth.” Somebody replied to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “I deposit my money.” It seems that the primary school students independently spent their school money, when necessary, where necessary. Similarly, every university should allow or approve small amount of research grant or research fund or research gift without any billing process. These are the motivational funds for the researcher. If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is serving to Bangladesh government is highlighting the limitations of education service in Bangladesh, he should have legal rights to get the surviving support/printed money of Bangladesh government. Every university teacher, founder, chairman, vice chancellor, director, researcher, professor should jointly continue the research practice to satisfy the word of university to satisfy the word of university teacher. There is also global limitation of knowledge culturing and right investment. Investment in higher education and research is the responsibility of a government. These are not

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the responsibilities of a person when a person/researcher/founder can not officially control the currency inflation of a country. A standard culturing process of knowledge in university is necessity for the development of science and technology, higher education, law, criminology, and personal excellency.

5 Acknowledgement

Sole author, Chief Director, PhD Research; Chief Director, Textile, Defence, and Law Research centre, RMIT; Chief Researcher, Textile, Color, and Material Research Centre, RMIT <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287> Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (**M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018**) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018; Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c, 2019d; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; M. A. Hossain, 2023ap; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2019) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (**M. A. Hossain, 2023ai, 2023am, 2023bi, 2023ci, 2023cj**) (Anowar Hossain, 2016; A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2023; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015b, 2015c, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; M. A. Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023ar, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bm, 2023bn; M. A. Hossain, 2023a; M. A. Hossain, 2023bo, 2023bp, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023bs, 2023bt; M. A. Hossain, 2023b; M. A. Hossain, 2023bu, 2023bv, 2023bw; M. A. Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; M. A. Hossain, 2023by, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc, 2023cd, 2023ce; M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; M. A. Hossain, 2023cf, 2023cg, 2023ch, 2023ci, 2023cj, 2023ck, 2023cl; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s, 2024t, 2024u, 2024v, 2024w, 2024y, 2024z; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024aa; Hossain, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, 2025g, 2025h, 2025j; Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025); name of father: late Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid, medical practitioner; permanent residence (PR): village: Purbo Nuthurchar, post office: K. Mohonpur (1990), police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia (PR by birth); nationality, national ID, passport and birth registration number: Bangladeshi,

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19862692620993890, A15988852/EE0444946/AF3831770, 003236; PhD (Doctor of Philosophy) application ID: 2612540, PhD student ID: 3820066, program name: DR213, PhD (fashion and textiles), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; lecturer on textile engineering (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh acknowledges RMIT University and the Australian government for funding through research training program (RTP) stipend scholarship, 2020-2025. Author, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>) also acknowledges ‘Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang’ (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7300-9271>) and ‘Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks’ (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3790-5148>) for their PhD supervision works at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

6 Proposal of quality funding at Textile, Color & Material Research Centre, City University, Bangladesh

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is asking quality funding at Textile, Color & Material Research Centre at City University, Bangladesh and/or research organization to the authority of City university and/or government of Bangladesh and/or foreign authority and/or United Nations (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025i).

7 Searching chief professor/senior professor category salary, office, and quality research fund on textile coloration

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, chief researcher is searching research fund to assess zero toxic coloration, natural material based textile coloration, and relevant field of textile technologies (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019) (A. Hossain, 2020) (M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018) (Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018) (Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018) (Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018) (Hossain, 2019d; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025i). Funding authority of City University and/or any government authority and/or non-government authority may extend the relevant research fund. There is scope of research and development in the relevant field of textile technology.

8 Searching chief professor/senior professor category salary of international standard, office, and quality research fund to national and international universities

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is offering BSc Engineering degree by thesis in textile technology, Master of Technology by thesis in textile technology, Master of Science by thesis in textile technology, MPhil degree by thesis in textile technology, PhD degree by thesis in textile technology, Postdoc degree by thesis in textile technology (M. A. Hossain, 2023au; Hossain, 2025d). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also offering Bachelor degree by thesis in law, Master degree by thesis in law, MPhil degree by thesis in law, PhD degree by thesis in law, Postdoc degree by thesis in law (M. A. Hossain, 2023au; Hossain, 2025b). Accordingly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is approaching and asking quality funding and quality platform at national and international universities. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will take 70% of the total tuition fees and university will take 30% of the total tuition fees. A subsidiary fund of university or scholarship, a government subsidiary fund or scholarship may be implemented to cover the costs of research fund, research student, and research professor (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bx; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024i; Hossain, 2025i).

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9 Author contribution and authorship status of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

The author has contribution in conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, research communications, planning and prediction, analysis, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role of the design of research, research idea or visualization, research and innovation, drafting of manuscript, editing of manuscript, and publication of manuscript.

10 Declaration of conflicting interests

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

11 Data availability

All data generated during the coalescing of this article are included, attached and briefly cited.

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12 If necessary, please visit online profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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13 Professional excellency of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13073.70249>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16990186>

Invitation of researchers in textile engineering in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17215.57765>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16960861>

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14 Legal authorization and signing

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16 Evidences of communication about research proposal, fund allotment and fund reservation at City University, Bangladesh

People's Republic of Bangladesh Office of the Notary Public-Bangladesh

S.N. ISLAM & ASSOCIATE'S
 Advocate & Notary Public
 (Whole Bangladesh)

According to the Section 8 (1)(h) of Notary ordinance 1961 Ad

Translated Copy

[City University Monogram]
 Date: 18/11/2019

Ref No. - City University/Reg./9083/2019

To,
 Mr. Md Anowar Hossain (Chief Researcher)
 Lecturer
 Textile Engineering Department
 City University

Subject: Regarding research projects and allocation of approvals.

Dear Sir,

This is hereby informing you, for your kind consideration that, Your Recommended Research Project: Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents [A Six Months Duration of Project, September, 2019 - February, 2020 and the allotment of the said research Tk. 1,00,000/- (One Lac) was approved by the university authorities. The authority has to be notified before starting the project. After receiving your letter 50% of the money allocated to start the project, 25% in terms of getting a Progress Report at the end of the half term and upon completion of the project, the Project Completion Report (PCR) will submit and the remaining amount will be disbursed immediately after receiving it.

In this regards you are requested to begin the work of your proposed research project as soon as possible.

Thanking you,
 Signature/ Illegible
 18/11/2019
 M.A Hannan
 Registrar
 City University

Permanent Certified University
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30 NOV 2019

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স্মারক নং- সিটি ইউনিভার্সিটি/রেজি./৯০৮৩/২০১৯ইং

তারিখ: ১৮/১১/২০১৯ইং

বরাবর,
 জনাব মোঃ আনোয়ার হোসেন (প্রধান গবেষক)
 প্রভাষক
 টেক্সটাইল ইঞ্জিনিয়ারিং বিভাগ
 সিটি ইউনিভার্সিটি।

বিষয়ঃ গবেষণা প্রকল্প এবং বরাদ্দ অনুমোদন প্রসঙ্গে।

জনাব,
 আপনার সদয় অবগতির জন্য জানানো যাচ্ছে যে, আপনার প্রস্তাবিত গবেষণা প্রকল্প Zero Toxic
 Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents [A
 Six Months Duration of Project, September, 2019- February, 2020] এবং উক্ত
 গবেষণার বরাদ্দ ১,০০,০০০/- (এক লক্ষ) টাকা বিশ্ববিদ্যালয় কর্তৃপক্ষ কর্তৃক অনুমোদিত হয়েছে।
 উক্ত প্রকল্পের কাজ শুরু করার অব্যবহিত পূর্বে কর্তৃপক্ষকে অবহিত করতে হবে। আপনার পত্র
 পাওয়ার পরে প্রকল্পের কাজ শুরু করার জন্য বরাদ্দকৃত অর্থের ৫০%, মেয়াদকালের অর্ধেককাল
 সমাপনান্তে সন্তোষজনক অগ্রগতির প্রতিবেদন (Progress Report) পাওয়ার শর্তে ২৫% এবং প্রকল্প
 কাজ পূর্ণ সমাপনান্তে Project Completion Report (PCR) জমা এবং তা গৃহীত হওয়ার পরপরই
 বরাদ্দকৃত অর্থের অবশিষ্ট ২৫% অর্থ ছাড় করা হবে।

এমতাবস্থায় আপনার প্রস্তাবিত গবেষণা প্রকল্পের কাজ যথাশীঘ্র সম্ভব শুরু করার জন্য আপনাকে
 অনুরোধ করা হলো।

ধন্যবাদান্তে

এম এ হোসেন
 রেজিস্ট্রার
 সিটি ইউনিভার্সিটি।

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 Secretary Public For Whole of Bangladesh
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 26 NOV 2019

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1

Research Proposal

On

**Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents
[A Six Months Duration of Project, September, 2019-January, 2020]**

Proposed By

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September-2019

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Research Track Record of Md. Anowar Hossain, Principal Investigator (PI):

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is presently a Lecturer in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka and a Ph.D researcher of Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka. He is a former Assistant Professor and Head of Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering and Technology, Jessore, Affiliated by University of Rajshahi. He is also a former Lecturer and Head of Department of Textile Engineering and Assistant Registrar (Additional), Newcastle University College, Chittagong, Affiliated by University of Chittagong. He worked as chairman & member of Examination Committee both for University of Rajshahi and University of Chittagong. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a former CEO of Bangladesh Textile and Fashion, Dhaka, former Coordinator of Gothic Design Ltd., Viyellatex Group, Tongi, former merchandiser of Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain studied two years Master of Technology in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) from University of Calcutta, India and also completed four years B.Sc. in Textile Engineering from City University, Dhaka. He published different research papers as principal author connected with international universities where twelve research papers with textile engineering based research in international peer reviewed journal. He is an author of three books in Textile Engineering, “Basic knowledge of Wet Processing Technology”, “Principle of Garments Production” and “Garments Technology for Merchandiser and Fashion Designer”. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has certified training on coated textile production and glass fabric manufacturing (KE Technical Textiles Ltd, India), Dyeing and Finishing, Spinning, Weaving and Knitting, Merchandising (National Institute of Textile Training, Research and Design NITTRAD, Savar, Dhaka, Faculty of Niederrhein University, Germany), Export and Import (DCCI Business Institute, Dhaka, Affiliated by ITC UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva) as well as other training in related profession of textile engineering. [Below mentioned national and foreign researchers are already connected with related fields of proposed project investigator (PI) and he has already Six (6) publications as first and corresponding author in international peer reviewed journal with all the mentioned national and foreign experts in textile coloration addressing the present working place, City University]

National consultants and experts in textile coloration:

- Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, Assistant Professor and Head, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka.
- Dr. Md. Nurul Absar, Professor and Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka.
- Dr. Ferdous ara Dilruba, Chief Scientific Officer, Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (BJRI), Dhaka.

Foreign Consultants and experts in textile coloration:

- Dr. AK Samanta, Professor and Former Chairman, Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India.
- Dr. Padma S. Vanakr, Professor & Principal Research FEAT Lab, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Kanpur, India.

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Introduction:

Bangladesh is presently exporting a good quantum of coloured and decorative textile products made of natural fibres like silk, cotton and jute mainly to Japan, USA, Korea, European community countries and African countries. Worldwide growing consciousness for eco-friendly production process is generating more and more customer's interests on natural fibre, natural dyes and natural finished based textile products, particularly for the export market due to having an approach of zero toxic coloration of cotton fabric with natural dyes under consideration of toxic free product and environment friendly production process. Considering the product development and production process corner, textile sector has the highest scope to apply this research work for attracting the value-added customer. But, till today there is a huge lack of research and development of natural dyeing and finishing based textile product.

However, there are some discrete reports available that indicate the application of natural dyes for producing uncommon shades on natural fibers like cotton (Anowar and et al. 2018, 2019, Cristea and Vilarem 2006; Gahlot et al. 2008; Sentikumar et al. 2002), jute (Samanta and Agarwal 2008a; Samanta and Agarwal 2007; Samanta et al. 2008b; Samanta and Konar 2012a; Samanta and Konar 2015; Samanta et al. 2010, 2011; Samanta et al. 2012b; Samanta et al. 2008c; Samanta et al. 2012b, 2009), silk (Gahlot et al. 2008; Javali et al. 2009; Katti et al. 1996; Mahale et al. 2003a; Mahale et al. 2003b; Sidhu and Grewal 2008; Vankar and Shankar 2008; Vinod et al. 2010), wool (Gahlot, Fatima, and Papnai 2008; Gulrajani et al. 2003; Shanker and Vankar 2005; Yoshizumi and Crews 2003). Hence there are ample scopes of doing scientific research on the application of natural dyes on cotton and other textiles aimed at obtaining newer shade with acceptable colour fastness behavior, uniform and reproducible colour yield through appropriate techniques. Simultaneous natural dyeing, natural mordanting and natural finishing process can be a new approach of technique which will minimize the process steps different cost related production like energy and total process cost. Reducing process cost will minimize total cost of the product in the export market, it will be highly beneficial to sustain in a competitive market if the expected research output can be applied successfully in Government and non-government textile mill at home and abroad.

Natural dyes are considered to be eco-friendly as these are obtained from renewable resources as compared to synthetic dyes which are derived from non-renewable petroleum resources. These are biodegradable and the residual vegetal matter left after extraction of dyes can be easily composted and used as fertilizer. They produce soft colours soothing to the eye which is in harmony with nature which is gradually gaining popularity due to its non-toxicity and eco-friendly character against possible unsafe ecotoxicity criteria of synthetic dyes. Most of the studies available for dyeing with natural dyes relates to cotton textiles and such studies on cotton are still insufficient to establish. Hence, there are ample scope of undertaking an integrated study in this area for cotton and chemically modified cotton to study its surface appearance, durability and dyeing of cotton and chemically modified cotton with natural dyes.

The research and development in natural dyed based textile products conducted by textile researcher has been confused to solve technological problem for the production of ecofriendly based textiles and earlier investigation prove that the standard technology and production aspects are the core barrier for the standardization and commercialization of nature friendly textiles and there is unlimited technical demand for ensuring novel production and synthesis method for production process. Currently developed only natural dyed based textiles have so much limitations and have synthetic mordanting application which is not ecofriendly and not fulfilling the requirements of nontoxic coloration of textiles and till today there is a huge lack of research and development of natural dyed and finished textile products as reviewed in literature.

Proposed research on Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural mordanting agent generated by natural dyes and selective natural mordanting agent through selective dyeing process and the completely ecofriendly products was not experimented till now and the output of this research may be a greater and attractive invention for the development of value added textiles with the theokotex based textiles as well as improve the textiles with significant and special properties like UV protection and antibacterial property etc. comparing to reviewed method and developed natural dyed based textiles and there is little/limited research has been conducted with the proposed materials and method. Natural dyeing and finishing in the stage of development process and still many important accomplishments are hidden with the success corner of related researchers due to unavailability of testing standards for clothing, lower fastness properties and reproducibilities are the question marks to the textile scientist for natural dyed based textiles.

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Review of Literature:

Anowar and et al. (2018) were experimented in earlier research on natural coloration that natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing. A combined green dyeing and mordanting method was applied on cotton fabric in which natural coloring agents were extracted from Diospyros malabarica (Green Gaub fruit) and Camellia sinensis (Green Tea Leaf) where ever green lemon juice had been used as a green mordanting agent and there is no artificial chemical was used during demodulation process of coloring agent, dyeing and mordanting. Both the treated and untreated fabric samples were tested for the mechanical properties (color fastness to washing and rubbing) and dyeing performance in terms of color fastness properties (light fastness) and color strength, K/S value. For dyeing with green gaub fruit, color fastness to wash and rubbing = Very excellent, color fastness to light = good and for dyeing with green tea leaf, color fastness to wash = very excellent, color fastness to rubbing = excellent, color fastness to light = good. An improved color strength, K/S value had been found for both dyeing with green gaub fruit and green tea leaf while mordanting was applied with green lemon juice.

Anowar and et al. (2018) studied on pollution free dyeing and mordanting is indicated as a creative innovation of textile coloration on cotton fabric in which natural dyes were extracted from Swietenia macrophylla (Mahogany leaf) and Musa acuminata (Green Banana Peel) as an unpolluted dyes and Citrus limon (L.) juice was applied as an unpolluted natural mordanting agent. There is no synthetic chemical was used during the whole progression in dyes extraction process and dyeing method. Both the treated and untreated fabric samples were tested for their dyeing performance in terms of color strength, K/S value and color fastness properties like color fastness to washing, rubbing and light. Higher K/S value of lemon mordanted sample was investigated by analysis of spectrophotometer for both dyeing with mahogany and green banana pill. Color fastness to washing and rubbing had been found moderately good for both dyeing with mahogany leaves and green banana pill with lemon mordanting. Moderately good color fastness to light had been found for dyeing with only mahogany leaves and green banana pill but improved light fastness was found for green banana pill with lemon mordanting. As per visual appearance, dyed fabric with green banana pill and lemon mordanting was found very even distribution of color on the surface of cotton fabric. An exceptionally attractive soft hand feel and color shading outcome was observed for dyeing with green banana pill comparing to mahogany leaves without having any additional application of synthetic softer which is the demand of both local and foreign customers in clothing industries

Anowar and et al. (2018) focused that a toxicity free cotton fabric coloration and antibacterial technique was developed where natural colorant curcumin and tannin were applied for investigating a substitute of toxic colorant. Considering the negative impacts of man-made dyes in environment, non-toxic coloring and sterile finishing was carried out with curcumin and tannin as non-toxic colorant quintessence from pure natural sources of Curcuma longa (Turmeric) and Camellia sinensis (Tea Leaf) using environment friendly lemon extracted (Natural Citric acid) solution as natural mordant and their color shading and functional outcomes were evaluated in variety of shades as compared with colour yield/outcomes with ferrous sulphate and copper sulphate as two most extensively practiced conventional chemical mordants. Critical performances of mordanted and unmordanted cotton fabric samples were tested for their color parameters like Colour Strength, K/S value and Colour fastness (color fastness to Washing, UV- Light and Rubbing) properties, besides measurement of other colour interaction parameters (L*, a*, b* and ΔE) as well as anti-bacterial performance as Per AATCC-100-2012 method. The dye absorption determined by color spectrophotometer showed higher color strength when treated with curcumin and tannin colorant in the presence of natural extracted citric acid from lemon as toxic free mordanting agent compared to mordanting with Ferrous sulphate as well as conventional mordanting with Copper Sulphate. Higher rubbing fastness was observed for both dyeing with Turmeric and Tea Leaves when mordanting with lemon and ferrous sulphate. Curcumin demonstrates a pharmacological properties that curcumin found effective against E. coli bacteria in laboratory experiment well as FTIR study of Turmeric with lemon mordanted sample was confirmed the natural crosslinking among cotton fibre cellulose, turmeric curcumin and lemon-citric acid. Consequently, this work has led to development of a process of concurrent natural dyeing and finishing with natural extracted agents on cotton with natural mordants to make the fabric colour full and anti-bacterial also. If the present work is trailed commercially to make it feasible, undoubtedly present finding of research may be an exceptional source of eco-garments production which has a higher demand in local and foreign customer.

Anowar and et al. (2018) investigated that eco-friendly dyeing on cotton fabric was conceded out with organic dyes distillate from organic extraction process of organic Tectonagrandis (Teak Leaf) and Azadirachta indica (Neem Leaf) using ecofriendly metallic mordants and natural mordants (Ferrous Sulphate as ecofriendly metallic mordant and Lemon juice as an organic mordant were used in the research work and their results were compared with results of copper sulphate as conventionally used mordant. All the treated and untreated cotton fabric samples were tested for their Colour Strength and Colour fastness (colour fastness to Washing, UV Light and Rubbing) properties, besides measurement of other colour interaction parameters (L*, a*, b* and ΔE) as well as antibacterial performance as Per AATCC-100-2012 method. Results of colour parameters showed lower ΔE values are obtained when treated with lemon mordanting agent for both the case of dyeing cum finishing treatment with Teak leaf and Neem leaf (though amongst the two dye extract used, Neem leaf extract showed higher K/S value) as compared to

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conventional mordanting with Copper Sulphate. While, Ferrous Sulphate render moderate K/S value than all due to inherent own colour of iron $FeSO_4$. Comparing lemon mordanting with conventional copper sulphate mordant, colour fastness properties of teal leaf extract with lemon mordanting are found to be better and is in the order of Rubbing Fastness > followed by colour fastness to Light > colour fastness to wash than that for synthetic mordanting, but for dyeing with extract of neem leaf with lemon mordanting showed very attractive colour fastness considering to all colour fastness properties studied here. In this study, a newer approach / attempt had been made to impart a simultaneous antibacterial finish along with above said natural dyeing. Hence, the antibacterial properties of neem leaf extract dyed cotton using lemon mordant sample resulted better reduction/killing of bacteria. Thus, this work has led to development of a process of simultaneous dyeing and finishing with natural agents on organic cotton with organic mordants to make the fabric colour full and anti-bacterial too.

Anowar and et al. (2019) reviewed on Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing can be established by developing completely eco-friendly natural dyes and natural finishing agent which can be applied on cotton textiles (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a newer technique of simultaneous Mordanting-Dyeing-Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process time, processing costs and effluent load as well as to develop the single step processes and also completely eco-friendly products of cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from an extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy. There is huge scope of commercialization of such Oeko-Tech (Eco-Friendly) products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile products for domestic and export market. Different selective natural dyes like teal leaf, turmeric, jackfruit wood, sappan wood, skin of onion, arjuna bark etc., bio-mordanting agent like bio-enzyme, harda, lemon as natural mordanting agents, extracted soyabean seed as natural chemical modification as well as natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent where all dyed and finished fabric can be scientifically tested by SEM, FTIR, DSC, HPLC, GCMS, TLC, CHNS, X-ray diffraction pattern etc.

Samanta and et. al (2003) and **Dedhia E.M (1998)** studied that growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products has created more interest on cotton fibre based natural dyeing and finishing. Productions of synthetic dyes are dependent on the petrochemical source and some of the synthetic dyes contain toxic/carcinogenic amines and are not eco-friendly. Contrary to this, most of the natural dyes as well as natural finish with few exceptions are based on vegetable/ animal origin and are renewable, biodegradable, energy-efficient and eco-friendly.

Kawahito, et al. (2002) have compared the dyeing of cellulosic fabric with natural indigo and synthetic indigo. Radhakrishnan as well as Ajita, et al. have reported the effect of different mordants on selective natural dyes. **Grierson, et al. (1995)** has studied colour fastness characteristics of some natural dyes. **Lee, et al. (2001)** have studied the colour fastness properties of some natural dyes by applying UV-absorbers. **Gupta, et al (1998)** have reported that the effect of chemical structure on light fastness property of some natural dyes.

Oda, et al. (2001) was studied the effect of phenyl ester functional group on photofading of carthamin on cellulose acetate. Most of the studies are sporadic and insufficient in developing scientific knowledge base on the subject. Therefore, very less study on simultaneous natural dyeing and finishing, dyeing process variables and characterisation etc.

Reviewed study shows that natural dyes was applied with synthetic mordanting agents on textile substrates and its feasibility of application has been positively remarked by the researcher in the area of textile coloration, but the application of completely biomordanting agents/natural mordanting agents/natural finishing agents, standardization of process development, industrial application and commercialization of natural dyed product are the major gaps of research and development in the area of natural dyeing and finishing which may be focused area of research in proposal on zero toxic coloration. Hence, an integrated scientific study for selective natural dye-fibre-mordanting system, for selective natural dyes and natural mordanting agents can be applied on cotton and other textiles is felt necessary, for establishing the ecofriendly process of textile colorations for natural dyed textiles.

The natural coloration on cotton fabric is an approach of zero toxic coloration of cotton fabric with natural dyes and natural mordanting agent will be the alternative way of conventional synthetic dyeing which is a threat of ecofriendly environment. Proposed technique can be implemented in the textile industries for having the nature friendly agro renewable sources of natural dyes. On the otherhand synthetic dyes is a petroleum sources of production. The concept and the workable procedures developed from the research can be transferred to industrial practice in home and abroad. The proposed research can provide simultaneous effect of dyeing, mordanting, technical finishing, ecofriendly coloration process in textiles is definitely a technological light in the door of colored textile production. Thus, there are sufficient scopes of doing scientific research on making standardization of technique, increasing color fastness to conventional process, adaptability, durability and suitability of process and product development.

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Objectives of Research:

- To develop completely eco friendly natural dyed and Natural Agent finished Cotton Textile Fabrics (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a Newer Technique of Simultaneous Natural Mordanting–Natural Dyeing–Natural Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process Time , Processing costs and Effluent Load (which has not been done earlier).
- To investigate the single step processes and also completely eco-Friendly Products of cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy.
- To analyse methods for specific identification of natural dyes on natural dyed and finished textile products for establishing natural dye mark.
- To commercialize of such oeko-tech (eco friendly) products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile products.

Materials and Methods:

Application of Different Biomordanting with Biomordanting Agents:

Effects of different degrees of premordanting, simultaneous mordanting, post mordanting with lemon leaves as natural mordanting agents and natural dye ability with selective natural dyes (say a banana pill, neem leaves, tea leaves, teak leaves, guava leaves, Jackfruit wood, basil leaves, eucalyptus leaves, pecker leaves, peach leaves as well as as per availability natural sources etc.) can be investigated. Effect of such biomodifications on colour parameters after dyeing of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified cotton and its colour fastness properties to light, washing, perspiration and rubbing can be studied. The photo fading behaviour of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified and dyed cotton materials after those modifications and pre-treatments and subsequent dyeing can be studied and an attempt can be taken to improve the same to a much better level of customer acceptability. Effects of different degree of chemical modifications on colour yield for the selective natural dyes can be studied. Cotton Textile materials dyed with natural dyes can be post-treated/finished with suitable natural agents for studying the effect of these after treatments on the improvement of colour yield, brightness and colour fastness behaviour of the dyed material. To improve the colour fastness properties for the selective natural dyes some pre or post-treatment with cationic or metallic complex compound or UV absorbers/suitable modifiers can be studied.

Process Development:

The fabrics can be pre-treated by the eco-friendly enzyme-based chemical pre-treatment processes for preparing it for simultaneous dyeing and finishing. After that different natural dyes say a banana pill, neem leaves, tea leaves, teak leaf, guava leaves, neem leaves, Jackfruit wood, basil leaves, eucalyptus leaves, pecker leaves, peach leaves as well as as per availability natural sources etc.) and natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent as well as selective mordanting agents can be applied on cotton fabric for trailing and experimentations on application of dyes and finishing agent on cotton and optimization of dyeing process variables for improved colour development and improvement of colour fastness, all analytical testing. Effects of variations of dyeing process variables on colour yield and dyeing kinetics for application of selective natural dyes on cotton and chemically modified cotton substrate can be investigated to understand the dyeing isotherm, rate of dyeing and other thermodynamic parameters for such dyeing. This will help to understand the dyeing behaviours of different natural dyes applied on cotton to get an idea of formulating better colour yield having specific standardized dyeing recipe for combined/compound shades by use of binary or ternary mixture of these natural dyes. For use of combination of natural dyes for generating compound shades, a study on the compatibility of such binary and a ternary mixture of dyes can be also studied, to understand and find a compatible combination of such dyes for cotton and chemically treated and modified cotton fabrics.

Process of Textile Properties and Dyeability Analysis:

Changes in structural features for different degrees of mordanting on cotton substrate can be investigated with the help of Spectrophotometer, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), FTIR Spectroscopy and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), High-Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPLC), Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GCMS), Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC), Carbon, Hydrogen, Nitrogen and Sulphur (CHNS) analyzer and X-ray diffraction pattern etc. and different fastness properties for explaining the major observations in these aspects. This will help to understand scientifically the scientific analysis of different changes in textile related property behaviour and dyeability in terms of changes in structural features of chemically modified cotton substrate along with changes in surface characteristics and durability etc.

Proposed By Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Principal Investigator

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Major activities to be undertaken as follows during the total project implementation period :

[Implemented By Md. Anowar Hossain, Principal Investigator (PI)]

	Experimental Work Phases	Research Lab
1.	Extraction of natural dyes from dyed cotton textiles and their identification.	Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University
2.	Study of extraction of different natural dyes in different media and study of the chemistry and colour characteristics of the colour component of selective natural dyes to establish standard method and optimum conditions of extracting those natural dyes from different sources	Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University
3.	Studies on dyeing process variables and effect of different mordanting agents / mordanting methods on colour yield and fastness behaviour.	Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University
4.	Studies on effect of different degree of chemical modifications of cotton textiles on colour yield behaviour of selective natural dyes as well as natural mordanting.	Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University Dyeing lab-Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari.
5.	Studies on effect of different degree of colour fastness behaviour of selective natural dyes as well as natural mordanting.	Wet Processing lab-Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (BJRI), Textile Dyeing lab-Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari.
6.	Studies on authentication of test methods of identification of natural dye from outside nation and International accredited laboratories and analysis of results.	FEAT lab, Indian Institute of Technology, IIT, Kanpur, India Textile Coloration Lab, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India
7.	Experimental Work-Phase –XII: Patenting and Publication of technical manuals/ notes Publication and Popularisation of natural dye standards at National and International level with establishing natural dye/finish mark to be implemented worldwide of natural dyed textiles.	City University
8.	Field Trial	Production Unit, Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari.

Expected Outcomes:

Feasibility of natural dyeing, natural mordanting, natural finishing will be studied to achieve an ecofriendly approach of zero toxic coloration of cotton fabric with natural dyes and natural mordanting agents which will be tested by different advanced analytical method of natural coloration.

Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing can be established by developing completely eco-friendly natural dyes and natural finishing agent which can be applied on cotton textiles (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a newer technique of simultaneous Mordanting-Dyeing-Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process time, processing costs and effluent load as well as to develop the single step processes and also completely eco-friendly products of cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from an extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy. There is huge scope of commercialization of such Oeko-Tech (Eco-Friendly) products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile products for domestic and export market.

Proposed By Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Principal Investigator

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), B.Sc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Researcher and Founder, Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Budget:	
Project activities with breakdown of cost of 1,50,000 BDT	Total Cost in BDT
Raw materials, Extraction, processing and experimentation charges: [Sample Collection (Natural Dyes) charge (10 Sample×500 BDT = 5000 BDT), Dyes preparation, Drying and Powder forming charge (10 Sample ×500 BDT = 5000 BDT), Machine charge for extraction of dyes: 5000 BDT, Fabric cost for trialing: 5000 BDT, Fabric pretreatment charge: 1500 BDT, Machine charge for dyeing and finishing (Laboratory stage trialing): 13000 BDT, Field trial = 5800 BDT]	35,300 BDT
Testing fees [Spectrophotometer (10 sample × 2000 BDT =20000 BDT), SEM-(5 sample × 2000 BDT =10000 BDT), Light fastness-(5 sample × 1000 BDT=5000 BDT), Color Fastness-(5 sample × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT), Wash Fastness (5 sample × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT), Color Fastness to perspiration (5 sample × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT)]	50,000 BDT
Conveyance, Research Coordination and Research Meeting Conveyance and allowance (Day Long) [Office/ residence to Jahangirnagar University (5 Day long × 300 BDT =1500 BDT), Residence to Mascom Composite (5 Day long×300 BDT=1500 BDT),Residence to Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (3 Day long × 500 BDT = 1500 BDT, Residence to Science Lab 3 Day long × 500BDT = 1500 BDT, Residence to SGS (Testing Lab) 2 Day long × 500 BDT=1000 BDT)] Conveyance and allowance (Half Day) [Office, Khagan to Jahangirnagar University (20 Day × 100 BDT=2000 BDT), Office to Mascom Composite Ltd. (20 Day×200BDT=4000 BDT),Permanent Campus to City Campus ,City University (10 Day× 500 BDT =5000 BDT)] Preliminary meeting with experts (2 expert×1000 BDT=2000 BDT), Meeting in experimental stage with experts (2 expert × 1000 BDT = 2000 BDT), Report preparation and review meeting (2 expert × 1000 BDT = 2000 BDT)] Mobile bill for raw material purchasing, Lab coordination, expert coordination and other coordination (6 Month × 1000 BDT= 6000 BDT).	30,000 BDT
Stationary and Administrative cost [Sample tube, Scissor, Tape, Tissue, Soap, Mask, Hand gloves, Sample file, Sample Swatch Board ,Aprone, Stapler, Punch m/c, Calculator, Pendrive, Filter paper, PH Strip, Seal, Tracing Paper, Note Book and others: 3000 BDT, Review allowance and study materials (Book/Journal): 2000 BDT, Networking and computer support (6 month× 500 BDT= 3000 BDT), Casual Personal Assistant Fees (10 days×400 BDT=4000 BDT), Refreshment for Lab assistant /Lab technician (20 Person×60 BDT=1200 BDT), Research Office access /Casual Office Refreshment (15 weeks×200 BDT=3000 BDT).	16200BDT
Report writing, edition and submission process Report writing allowance: 3000 BDT, Computer Compose allowance: 5000 BDT, Graphical Design & Edition allowance: 2000 BDT, Report Edition allowance: (5 time × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT, Printing and Drafting: (5 time × 200 BDT =1000 BDT, 10 Copy Thesis Binding: (10 copy × 250 BDT = 2500 BDT)	18,500BDT
Total	1,50,000BDT

[Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will oversee the overall project and he will spend 20 hours/week as project investigator (additional duty of research and development), City University in different research laboratories like Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University, wet processing lab-Bangladesh Jute Research Institute, Textile Chemistry lab-City University, Dyeing lab-Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari as well as others laboratory as per needs of proposed research.]

[A subsidiary fund (20,000 BDT) for working with research graded foreign lab (natural coloration lab, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India) may be included with proposed budget/replaced with some activities (if possible) although foreign visit has been bamed in notification]

[Breakdown of cost may be changed/replaced by the principal investigator as per suitability of research progression during practical implementation of proposed research work]

Six Months/Twenty Four Weeks Timeline to Complete the Research:

Proposed By Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Principal Investigator

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Ph.D Researcher, School of Fashion and Textiles
RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
M. Tech. in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Mobile: +61 452209738, +8801732681104

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head
Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Date: 22/11/2021

Professor Mir Akhter Hossain
Registrar
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Letter of withdrawal the sanctioned research fund BDT 1, 00,000 (one lac), approved for Md. Anowar Hossain, lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent campus, academic year: 2019-20.

Dear Sir,

I would like to notify that I am a lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science and Engineering; presently I am pursuing Ph.D research at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia funded by RTP stipend scholarship, an Australian Government Research program. I got a letter of "study leave" from registrar office, city university approved by Mr. M A Hannan, former Registrar, City University on 26 January 2020, ref: City University/Faculty/BSTE/4029/2020 and I left Bangladesh on 28 January 2020 and commenced Ph.D research at School of Fashion and Textiles on 5 February 2020.

In these circumstances, I would like to withdraw the official allotment of approved research fund BDT 1, 00, 000 (one lac), project duration: six months, academic year 2019-2020, notified by registrar office on 18 November 2019, proposal accepted by the committee of research cell, City University to continue the proposed research works on "zero toxic coloration on cotton fabric with natural dyes and natural mordanting agents" at office location, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, permanent campus and research location at chemistry lab, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka.

Thanks

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Supporting information

Letter of research reporting issued by registrar office on 17 November 2021

Letter of study leave

Copy forwarded To

Professor (Dr.) Md. Humaun Kabir
Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Dean, Faculty of Science and Engineering

A/Professor (Dr.) Saiful Islam
Former Head, Department of Textile Engineering

16.1 Research Proposal

- Sabbih Hossain Rangan

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Institute, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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- sabbih.hossain@gmail.com

To: me · Tue, Oct 22, 2019 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Mr. Hossain

Please find the attached files. And send me the scanned copy of your reply by this afternoon.

Thank you.

S M Sabbih Hossain

Assistant Professor

Department of English

City University, Bangladesh

2 attachmentsDownload all

○

[Document 22 Oct 2019 11 11 am 1.jpgjpg · 1.3 MB](#)

○

[Document 22 Oct 2019 11 11 am 2.jpgjpg · 2.4 MB](#)

- Anowar Hossain

To: Sabbih · Tue, Oct 22, 2019 at 4:08 PM

Message Body

Dear Sir,

I acknowledge for primary selection of research funding and I am accepting the revised budget, one lac taka (only) for the research proposal on “Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents”.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain

Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Permanent Campus.

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To

S. M. Sabbih Hossain

Member –Secretary

Research Cell

City University, Dhaka

Subject: Letter of Acceptation for the Revised Budget.

Dear Sir,

I acknowledge for primary selection of research funding and I am accepting the revised budget, one lac taka (only) for the research proposal on “Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents”.

Thanking you

Md. Anowar Hossain

Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Permanent Campus.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh);
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

October 22, 2019

Md. Anwar Hossain
Lecturer
Department of Textile Engineering
City University
13/A, Panthapath, Dhaka

Subject: Regarding your Research Proposal

Mr. Hossain

It is my pleasure to inform you that your research proposal: *Zero Toxic Coloration Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents* is primarily selected for the 'funding' from the Research Cell, City University.

The budget you provided is reviewed and revised, and is attached to this letter. Please, go through the revised budget and reply to this letter with your comment (i.e. whether you accept it or not).

Thank you.

S. M. Sabbih Hossain
Member-Secretary
Research Cell
City University

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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Project activities with breakdown of cost of 1,00,000 BDT	Total Cost in BDT
Law materials, Extractions, processing and experimentation charges: Dye's Collection (Natural Dyes) charge (10 Sample×300 BDT = 3000 BDT), Dyes preparation, drying and Powder forming charge (10 Sample ×300 BDT = 3000 BDT), Machine charge for extraction of dyes: 5000 BDT, Fabric: 5000 BDT, Fabric pretreatment charge: 1500 BDT, Chemical/Apparatus: 5000BDT, Machine charge for dyeing and finishing (Laboratory stage trialing): 2000 BDT, Machine charge for dyeing and finishing (Field trialing): 10800 BDT]	30,000 BDT
Testing fees Spinning/Retraction (10 Sample × 1000 BDT =10000 BDT), SEM/FTIR sample × 2000 BDT =4000 BDT, Light fastness-(5 sample × 1000 BDT=5000 BDT), Color Fastness-(5 sample × 1,000 BDT =5000 BDT), Wash Fastness (5 sample × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT), Color Fastness to perspiration (5 sample × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT)	30,000 BDT
Research Meeting [Preliminary meeting with experts (2 expert×2000 BDT=4000 BDT), Meeting in experimental stage with experts (2 expert × 2000 BDT = 4000 BDT)]	8,000 BDT
Research Coordination with Pre-mentioned Laboratories Conveyance and allowance (Day Long) [Office/ residence to Jahangirnagar University (5 Day long × 300 BDT =1500 BDT), Residence to Mascom Composite (5 Day long×300 BDT=1500 BDT), Residence to Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (5 Day long × 500 BDT = 1500 BDT, Residence to Science Lab 5 Day long × 500 BDT = 1500 BDT) Conveyance and allowance (Half Day) [Office, Khagan to Jahangirnagar University (20 Day × 100 BDT=2000 BDT), Office to Mascom Composite Ltd. (20 Day×300 BDT=6000 BDT), Permanent Campus to City Campus ,City University (15 Day× 350 BDT =5250 BDT)]	16,000 BDT
Stationary and Administrative cost [Sample tube, Sample Box, Detergent, Mask, Hand gloves, Mask, Sample file, Sample Swatch Board, Pendrive, Filter paper, PH Strip, Seal, Tracing Paper, Note Book and others: 9750 BDT, Refreshment for Lab assistant /Lab technician in experimental stages (20 Person×60 BDT=1200 BDT)]	6,000 BDT
Report writing, edition, review and submission process [Report writing, edition and graphical Design: 6000 BDT, Review of report with expert: 5000 BDT, Printing and Drafting: (5 time × 300 BDT =1500 BDT, 10 Copy Thesis Binding: (10 copy × 300 BDT = 3000 BDT)]	10,000 BDT
Total: One Lac Taka Only	1,00,000 BDT

[Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will oversee the overall project and he will spend 20 hours/week as project investigator (additional duty of research and development), City University in different research laboratories like Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University, wet processing lab-Bangladesh Jute Research Institute, Textile Chemistry lab-City University, Dyeing lab-Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari as well as others laboratory as per needs of proposed research.]

[A subsidiary fund (20,000 BDT) for working with research grant/foreign aid (national government aid, Department of Textile and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India) is being proposed as additional budget and/or the cost may be replaced with some activities (if possible) although foreign visit has been excluded in notification]

[Breakdown of cost/Categories of cost may be changed/replaced by the project investigator as per suitability/reality of research progression during practical implementation of proposed research work as the work is laboratory based.]

Prepared By Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Research Cell City University

Notice

December 17, 2020

This is for your information that a meeting regarding the progress of the research project/s has been arranged by the Research Cell, City University on December 22, 2020 (Tuesday) at 10:30 a.m. at Pro-Vice-Chancellor's office. All the Principal Investigators are hereby requested to attend the meeting on due time.

(S. M. Sabbih Hossain)
Member-Secretary
Research Cell
City University

To:

1. Udayshankar Sarkar, Lecturer, Dept. of Business Administration
2. Rashedul Islam, Lecturer, Dept. of Business Administration
3. Md. Shakil, Lecturer, Dept. of Business Administration
4. Md. Anwar Hossain, Lecturer, Dept. of Textile
5. Shams Ul Islam, Lecturer, Dept of EEE
6. Md. Moniruzzaman Bhuyan, Lecturer, Dept. of ME
7. S. M. Sabbih Hossain, Assistant Professor, Dept. of English

16.2 Regarding the progress of your research project

- S. M. Sabbih Hossain

To: me, and 5 others · Thu, Dec 17, 2020 at 1:41 PM

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Message Body

Please,

Find the attached file for a notice regarding the progress of the project.

Thank you.

With regards

(S. M. Sabbih Hossain)
Assistant Professor
Department of English
CITY UNIVERSITY
Permanent Campus: Khagan, Savar, Dhaka
City Campus: 13/A, Panthapath, Dhaka
Bangladesh
Mobile: +880 1717-049905
WhatsApp: +880 1717-049905
email: sabbih.hossain@cityuniversity.edu.bd / sabbih.hossain@gmail.com

17 Evidences of peer review of journal and publication

IntechOpen – Your Chapter is Published

- Sandra Maljavac
- sandra.m@intechopen.com

To: me · Thu, Sep 10, 2020 at 6:00 PM

Message Body

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Dear Dr. Hossain,

We are pleased to let you know that your chapter has now been published online. Congratulations!

Page | 71

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Please check your publication promptly to ensure that it corresponds to the final version of your chapter.

Please feel free to share it with your colleagues and peers, and on social media.

Regards,

Sandra Maljavac
Author Service Manager

IntechOpen
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London: 5 Princes Gate Court, London, SW7 2QJ, UK
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IntechOpen - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Thu, Aug 27, 2020 at 1:46 PM

Message Body

Page | 72

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that all is well.

I have received the following email form our technical editors:

Corrections from the proof correction form have also been updated as per copy editing guidelines.

We have raised 11 queries to the author in the attached PDF. Please advise

Upon receiving your approval, we will do the required changes and re-upload the final package to panel. Thank you!

Please respond to these new queries as soon as you can so we can proceed with the final book preparation.

Regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

+44 20 8089 5702 | intechopen.com

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London: 10 Lower Thames Street, London, EC3R 6AF,
UK

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh); MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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IntechOpen - Action Required - Proof Corrections - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

Page | 73

- Ms. Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Fri, Jul 31, 2020 at 1:43 AM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Your chapter in the book under the working title "Chemistry and Technology of
Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments," ISBN 978-1-78985-997-3 is ready for
proof corrections.

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Page | 74

Once the rest of the book is ready, it will become part of the broader publication.

If you have any questions, feel free to contact me by phone or email.

Cordially,

Ms. Sandra Maljavac
Author Service Manager

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- Expand previously seen (1)
 - Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Mon, Aug 3, 2020 at 12:56 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Thank you, I have forwarded the corrections to our technical editors.

In case they'll have any additional questions, I'll let you know.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder, Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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All the best,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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- Re: IntechOpen - Action Required - Proof Corrections - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

Ms. Sandra Maljavac

CcBcc

Dear Ms. Sandra,

Thanks for your correction comments and working for improving the book chapter.

I have attached (pdf and word file) here all queries for your kind attention. Please try to shape this chapter by maintaining the “picture and text citation sequence” for readers easy understanding.

I have also uploaded the file in online system.

Please let me know if you face further difficulties to understand my comments for your edition process.

Page | 76

Thanks

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Friday, July 31, 2020, 05:43:25 AM GMT+10, Ms. Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com> wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Your chapter in the book under the working title "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments," ISBN 978-1-78985-997-3 is ready for proof corrections.

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DEADLINE: 06 August, 2020

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2. In the Typeset Proof, carefully examine *all* the Author Queries [AQ] provided in the table on the first page;
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Also, keep in mind that making changes to the content at this stage, such as

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This is the final round of corrections before the publication of your work and further editing will not be possible.

Once the rest of the book is ready, it will become part of the broader publication.

If you have any questions, feel free to contact me by phone or email.

Cordially,

Ms. Sandra Maljavac
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2 attachments

Out of Office Re: IntechOpen - Action Required - Proof Corrections - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Jasna Bozic

To: me · Mon, Aug 3, 2020 at 8:06 AM

Message Body

Thank you for your email.

I am currently out of the office and will be back on August 17, 2020.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
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International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

My colleague, Ms. Sandra Maljavac (sandra.m@intechopen.com) will handle your inquiries and provide you with any assistance that you may need until my return.

Kind regards,
Jasna

Jasna Bozic | Author Service Manager
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- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Mon, Aug 3, 2020 at 7:56 AM

Message Body

Thank you for your email.

I am currently out of the office and will be back on August 3rd, 2020.

My colleague, Ms. Jasna Bozic (jasna.b@intechopen.com) will handle your inquiries and provide you with any assistance that you may need until my return.

Kind regards,
Sandra

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IntechOpen - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Fri, Jul 10, 2020 at 12:46 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that you are doing well.

Our technical editors are currently working on your chapter and have sent me the following query:

- While editing, our editor found that the reference citations are missing in the manuscript but references are present. Kindly advise.

Please insert the reference citations in the text. I'm sending you the last version of the chapter attached to this email.

Looking forward to your response,

Sandra

--

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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- Expand previously seen (5)
- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Thu, Jul 16, 2020 at 1:56 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Thank you, I will forward your updated chapter.

Regards,

Sandra

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), B.Sc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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FULL WAIVER - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Mon, Jun 29, 2020 at 4:56 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that you are doing well.

Since you haven't responded to none of my emails and we need to proceed with the book project, I would hereby like to grant a full waiver for the publication of your chapter.

This would save its contents and we still be able to enrich the final book product.

Please let me know if you agree with this offer.

Regards,

Sandra

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
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- Expand previously seen (1)
- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Tue, Jun 30, 2020 at 12:51 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Thank you for the confirmation.

I'll send you the typeset proof once it is ready.

Regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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London: 10 Lower Thames Street, London, EC3R 6AF,

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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh); MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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URGENT- Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Wed, Jun 3, 2020 at 1:22 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that all is well on your side.

Please get in touch with me regarding your participation on the project. This task is **urgent**.

I am looking forward to your response.

Kind regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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Show trimmed content

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Wed, Jun 10, 2020 at 1:26 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Unfortunately, I still haven't received a response from your side.

Please note that any offer you may give will help us support the project financially.

I hope that you will respond and that we can continue with our collaboration.

Best,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 03. 06. 2020. 09:22, Sandra Maljavac wrote:

I hope that all is well on your side.

Please get in touch with me regarding your participation on the project. This task is **urgent**.

I am looking forward to your response.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Kind regards,

Sandra

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On 28. 05. 2020. 12:40, Sandra Maljavac wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope to find you well.

Please let me know if you would be able to cover the minimum of 150 GBP.

We would be very grateful for your help in these regards and hope that you will response positively.

All the best,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 21. 05. 2020. 10:17, Sandra Maljavac wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Thank you for your reply, I appreciate your comprehensive explanation.

I understand your position and, if it were possible, would grant you a full waiver for the publication of your work.

However, we have already granted several full waivers in this project and the financial stats do not allow me to offer one to you as well.

For this reason, I kindly ask you to think about the amount that you would be able to pay in order to support the project's sustainability.

Even a smaller amount of, e.g. 150 GBP would help us to cover the basic expenses of processing your chapter and publishing it online.

Please let me know the amount that you would be able to afford, it would mean a lot to us.

Looking forward to your response,

Sandra

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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On 21. 05. 2020. 08:45, Anowar Hossain wrote:

Hi Sandra Maljavac,

I am very happy to work with you without payment and I am really sorry to response with your office that I am not prepared for publication of my book chapter under any payment condition. As contribution, I can just work for the development of publication, I can't pay, this is my professional limitation of any publication process.

Please I will be so much thankful if you avoid to send me discount message, I didn,t ask you for giving me any discount.

May I also request your office to publish free of cost as I wrote this manuscript for Intech.open, not for other publisher and as contributory support I gave you original experimental work, not as usual chapter writing. If you are not ready to publish free of cost, please give me back my manuscript and kindly send me the cancel notification of your acceptance due to disagree of author payment.

I think it will be my best reponse for your kind attention regarding payment issue for the publication of accepted chapter in the book of "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments".

Thanks

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Wednesday, May 20, 2020, 06:29:50 PM GMT+10, Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com> wrote:

Page | 88

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that you are doing well.

Unfortunately, I still haven't received your response.

In the meantime, I have discussed your chapter's registration with my Manager and we are open to offer you a 60% discount to the fee.

This would lower it to 560 GBP. Of course, the amount can be split into parts or among different sources that would cover it.

Please let me know if the discount could be acceptable to you.

Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 13. 05. 2020. 10:06, Sandra Maljavac wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that all is well on your side.

Please get in touch with me regarding your participation on the project.

I am looking forward to your response.

Kind regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 06. 05. 2020. 08:14, Sandra Maljavac wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that you are doing well.

Since we haven't spoken for a while, I just wanted to check in to see if you have spoken to your library's management or found any other source of funding?

Please send me an update and let me know if there is anything I can help you with.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

Page | 90

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On 29. 04. 2020. 09:31, Sandra Maljavac wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Our authors are usually able to confirm the number of books their library or university will order prior to the book publication.

This is because, once the book is out, we have not way in managing your registration any longer and cannot generate an invoice retroactively.

Also, please note that your library can purchase books of any title, it doesn't have to be this book that you are currently contributing to.

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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh); MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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The following book will also be ready for publication in the following months, I believe it could be of interest for

you: <https://www.intechopen.com/welcome/36eb1ed7179e0790a029523c97f1df04>

Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 29. 04. 2020. 01:54, Anowar Hossain wrote:

Hi Sandra,

Thanks for your explanation.

But I have no way to confirm the number of copy as it is fully controlled by university administration.

I can only make the purchase requisition after having the book in ready condition & all marketing process will have to deal by your intech. office and I have no rights to involve with this process.

Please give me a list of all of your textile engineering book if I need I will give purchase requisition.

Thanks

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Tuesday, April 28, 2020, 04:37:18 PM GMT+10, Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com> wrote:

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Dear Dr. Hossain,

We can define the quantity of book the library would buy now and the payment can be done after the book publication.

Please note that I need this information prior to the final publication because I need to plan the project's sustainability and report on its financial stats.

We would be grateful if you could contact you library and inquire regarding their funding abilities and if they could order the mentioned 9 hard copies (9 * 90 GBP = 810 GBP).

This way we could resolve the issue of your chapter's funding and the fee would be covered by the book purchase.

We are an OpenAccess publisher and all chapters will be available online or in PDF form. However, the PDF version of the book as a whole will not be available to our readers- they will need to purchase it in hard copy.

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In case a book shows an outstanding performance, we will notify our authors on time.

Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 27. 04. 2020. 22:41, Anowar Hossain wrote:

Hi Sandra,

As per your below mail reference I can fill the form of library when the book will be available in online for selling and library office will ensure library copy both in online & hardcopy for library study reference and my study support, but the quantity of book & price everything will be done by library administration as per rules of university and your Intech. office will be responsible for marketing & selling your book.

Additional inquiry from for my understanding: As I know, Intech is a open access publisher, please let me know if your book is available in online, why readers/library should purchase your book and if you sell the book what will be benefit for authors.

Thanks

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Monday, April 27, 2020, 04:34:21 PM GMT+10, Sandra Maljavac sandra.m@intechopen.com wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Thank you for your response.

Please find attached the list of chapters and authors whose chapters will be included in the final publication.

The official PDF of the book hasn't yet been generated so I can't send it to you, but this list reflects the work that we have collected so far.

As you can see, we will even include the editor's chapter. Please feel free to use this list and send it to your library.

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I am sure that you will find the titles of interest as they all include very relevant and up-to-date research results.

Please let me know if your library would be interested to order several book copies (90 GBP per copy). They would need to order 9 copies so that we can grant the 40% discount offer.

We will make sure to send one hard copy to you for free.

Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 26. 04. 2020. 07:41, Anowar Hossain wrote:

Dear Madam,

Hope you are fine & well protected from COVID 19.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Sorry I am responding so delay when you are discussing with payment issue as I have a same reply again and again that I am completely unable to pay publication fees if you want to support my progress i.e fine.

Option as a Ph.D Researcher at RMIT University:

As per your option asked in previous mail, before confirming any book order at RMIT University I need to know all chapters and book in ready condition if any chapter matches with my present project here as study materials I have a rights to fill the requisition form to the library for your book purchasing.

Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, M.Tech.

Ph.D Researcher

RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

On Monday, April 20, 2020, 04:11:45 PM GMT+10, Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com> wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Thank you for your reply.

Please note that we have discussed the payment as early as mid-March where you have also expressed your inability to pay.

I have then sent you a list of options that might help you and haven't received your response since.

However, in order to save your work and progress, I am able to offer you a **40% discount** which would lower the fee to **840 GBP**.

This amount can be split into monthly installments or I can extend the payment deadline, if necessary.

Please let me know what you think. I am looking forward to your response.

Cordially,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 18. 04. 2020. 09:11, Anowar Hossain wrote:

Sandra Maljavac

Author Service Manager

Office of [intech. open](http://intech.open)

Dear Madam,

Thanks for your acceptance of my manuscript submission as a chapter of a book edited by Professor A K Samanta.

I am little bit confused with the below mail of payment.

Please proceed my publication without charging me.

Thanks for your kind acceptance with zero cost publication process.

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Friday, April 17, 2020, 12:00:12 AM GMT+10, Sandra Maljavac sandra.m@intechopen.com wrote:

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Dear Dr. Hossain,

Your OAPF Proforma Invoice is available on your Author Panel.

CHAPTER TITLE: A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural Coloration on Natural Fibre
 BOOK TITLE: Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments
 PROFORMA INVOICE NO.: 1641-2020
 YOUR PAYMENT IS DUE ON: 09 May, 2020

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Thank you for your attention regarding this matter.

 This is an automated message.
 Please contact your Author Service Manager
 for further assistance.

DISCOUNT OFFER- Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Wed, May 20, 2020 at 2:29 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

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I hope that you are doing well.

Unfortunately, I still haven't received your response.

In the meantime, I have discussed your chapter's registration with my Manager and we are open to offer you a 60% discount to the fee.

This would lower it to 560 GBP. Of course, the amount can be split into parts or among different sources that would cover it.

Please let me know if the discount could be acceptable to you.

Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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IntechOpen - Past Due OAPF Payment Reminder

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Sun, May 24, 2020 at 8:00 PM

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Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

According to our records we have not yet received your OAPF payment for:

CHAPTER TITLE: A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural Coloration on Natural Fibre
 BOOK TITLE: Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments
 PROFORMA INVOICE NO.: 1641-2020

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Thank you for your attention regarding this matter.

IntechOpen - Past Due OAPF Payment

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Thu, May 14, 2020 at 8:00 PM

Message Body

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Dear Dr. Hossain,

We would like to inform you that your OAPF payment deadline has passed.

CHAPTER TITLE: A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural Coloration on Natural Fibre

BOOK TITLE: Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

PROFORMA INVOICE NO.: 1641-2020

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If you feel that you have received this message in error or have already settled the above, please send a copy of the payment slip so that we may update our records.

Thank you for your attention regarding this matter.

IntechOpen - OAPF Payment Notification

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Thu, Apr 16, 2020 at 8:00 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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CHAPTER TITLE: A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural Coloration on Natural Fibre
 BOOK TITLE: Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments
 PROFORMA INVOICE NO.: 1641-2020
 YOUR PAYMENT IS DUE ON: 09 May, 2020

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Thank you for your attention regarding this matter.

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 Please contact your Author Service Manager
 for further assistance.

- Expand previously seen (9)
- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Wed, May 13, 2020 at 2:06 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that all is well on your side.

Please get in touch with me regarding your participation on the project.

I am looking forward to your response.

Page | 102

Kind regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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IntechOpen - OAPF Payment Reminder

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Mon, May 4, 2020 at 8:00 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

This is a reminder that your OAPF payment due date is approaching.

CHAPTER TITLE: A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural Coloration on Natural Fibre

BOOK TITLE: Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

PROFORMA INVOICE NO.: 1641-2020

PAYMENT DUE: 09 May, 2020

Please proceed to your Author Panel to complete your payment:

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Thank you for your attention regarding this matter.

URGENT- response needed

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Tue, Apr 14, 2020 at 2:59 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that all is well on your side.

Please get in touch with me regarding your participation on the project.

I am looking forward to your response.

Kind regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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IntechOpen - OAPF Payment

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Thu, Apr 9, 2020 at 4:01 AM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Your OAPF Proforma Invoice is now available on your Author Panel.

CHAPTER TITLE: A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural Coloration on Natural Fibre

BOOK TITLE: Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

YOUR PAYMENT IS DUE ON: 09 May, 2020

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IntechOpen - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Mon, Mar 30, 2020 at 11:47 AM

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope to find you well.

Please find attached the editor's comments regarding your chapter and the requested revision.

I am at your disposal in case of further questions or concerns.

Kind regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

+44 20 8089 5700 | intechopen.com

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IntechOpen - Final Notice of Acceptance - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Fri, Apr 3, 2020 at 5:00 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Following the submission of your revised chapter, please find your formal Notification of Chapter Acceptance attached to this email. Congratulations once again on your acceptance!

Next Step: Language Copyediting and Typeset

In order to ensure the highest quality of published content, your chapter will now enter Language

Copyediting and Typeset. Our Language Copyeditors will proofread your chapter and improve grammar, spelling, style, and accuracy if necessary, while our Technical Editors prepare your chapter for online publication.

A finalized version of your work will be sent to you to be reviewed before publication.

Page | 106

Your book will also be made available to buy in hardback print version! If you pre-order your hardback now you will receive another copy for free, applicable only on the first order you place. All contributing authors can also benefit from this exclusive promotion via the Author panel <http://mts.intechopen.com/account/login>. Encourage each contributor to pre-order and redeem their own free print copy.

If you have any additional questions or concerns, do not hesitate to contact me.

Cordially,

Sandra Maljavac
Author Service Manager

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IntechOpen - Minor Review Requested - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Mon, Mar 30, 2020 at 11:46 AM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I am pleased to inform you that your chapter titled "A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Coloration on Natural Fibre," submitted to the book under the working title "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments," has been reviewed. The Editor has accepted your full chapter but requested that you implement some minor changes outlined in the review comments.

In the attachment you will find recommendations/suggestions for changes from the Editor(s) that would improve the overall quality of your chapter.

Current Step: Upload Revision

Upload your revised chapter on your Author Panel incorporating the review comments within the next 3 days.

Next Step:

Language Copyediting and Typeset Proof. Once your revision is uploaded, your paper will undergo specialized proofreading and editing to improve grammar, spelling, style, and accuracy at no additional charge, while our Technical Editors prepare your chapter for online publication.

By way of saying thank you for your hard work, when your full chapter is accepted for publication you can pre-order your book and get one print copy for free on the first order you place. All contributing authors can benefit from this exclusive promotion available only through your Author Panel.

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Cordially,

Sandra Maljavac
 Author Service Manager

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Chapter Submission for the book of "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments (ISBN 978-1-78985-998-0)" edited by Professor A K Samanta

- Anowar Hossain

To: sandra.m@intechopen.com · Wed, Mar 18, 2020 at 7:21 AM

Message Body

Sandra Maljavac

**Author Service Manager, IntechOpen
10 Lower Thames Street, London, EC3R 6AF, UK**

Page | 108

Dear Madam,

Please below chapter is being submitted both in PDF and word format for the book of "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments (ISBN 978-1-78985-998-0)" edited by Professor A K Samanta. I am fail to upload electronically as I have nothing to mention funding option which is the requirement to fill the second step of online uploading.

A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles

Md. Anowar Hossain

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Thanks for your kind action to publish my chapter.

Regards

Md. Anowar Hossain

Ph.D Researcher, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

2 attachmentsDownload all

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- Expand previously seen (2)
- Sandra Maljavac

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To: me · Mon, Mar 23, 2020 at 4:22 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that you are doing well.

Since we haven't spoken for a while, I just wanted to check in to see if you have reviewed my proposed solutions?

Please send me an update and let me know if there is anything I can help you with.

Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

Subject: your chapter proposal is accepted and see in your author's panel in intech open site for book and also to See the mail to me from Ms Sandra Maljavac as new author service manager of IntechOpen - for the book on Chemistry and Technology of Natu...

- Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta

To: me, Cc: Prof. · Sat, Feb 15, 2020 at 11:35 PM

Message Body

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>

Sent: Friday, 14 February 2020, 17:58

To: anwar hossain

Subject: Fw: See the mail to me from Ms Sandra Maljavac as new author service manager of IntechOpen - for the book on Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments-- asking new chapter proposal

Dear anwar ,

Your chapter proposal is accepted with minor modification desired by the editor .

See the mail from new Author Service manager -Ms Sandra Maljavac to me for In Tech open wishing new chapter proposals alert to me when it will arrive etc

So do it now without delay ...to submit your full chapter with abstract after signing in with registeted id and password in In Tech open .com -under Book section by signing on ---and send

the same by mail also to ms sandra maljavac as new author service manager of intech , and also uploading it in intech open book site from author's panel . Get all your communicated transaction and communication for appointing you as aithor of this book from document and history menu in author's panel of you . Submit full chapter now as soon as possible to ms sandra maljavac (e mail : sandra.m@intechopen.com) .

Page | 110

See my comments as editor in tour aithor panel in intech open site by signing on there to see my all suugestons i.e to change title and to improve the chapter presentation as per template available in author's panel. Do not give too much shades and pictures . Give all colorometric measurements and fastness for all important shades with setails of mordanting and dyeing process and conditions for each shade given.

Thanks

Prof A k Samanta

From: Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com>

Sent: Friday, February 14, 2020 5:38 PM

To: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>

Subject: Re: Wecome to Ms Sandra Maljavac as new author service manager of IntechOpen - for the book on Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

Dear Dr. Samanta,

Thank you for your email and your warm welcome.

I am happy to be on board with you on the project and will send you an update as soon as new chapters arrive.

Also, I will notify you once the review for your chapter comes in.

Have a nice day,

Sandra

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 14. 02. 2020. 12:44, Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta wrote:

Ms Sandra Maljavac
 Author Service Manager
 In Tech Open

for the Book on Chemistry and Technology of Natural and synthetic dyes and pigments

+44 20 8089 5700 | intechopen.com

Rijeka: Janeza Trdine 9, 51000 Rijeka, Croatia

London: 10 Lower Thames Street, London, EC3R 6AF, UK

Dear Sandra madam,

I welcome you as new author service manager for the book on Chemistry and
 Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments to be published by In Tech
 Open.

Pls see that i have done and completed review of new chapter proposal for Dr Anowar
 Hossain . Ask Dr anowar Hossain and others who have not yet uploaded their full
 chapter , to send/upload full chapter as soon as possible .

If any new chapter proposal is uploaded or registered , let me know with Mail alert to

complete my review soon.

My chapter is still under review. As soon as you get the review report, send it to me for action, if any to do.

Page | 112

Hoping everything well to complete this book within the time limit

Prof A K Samanta

Professor and Former HOD, DJFT, IJT, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

From: Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com>

Sent: Thursday, February 13, 2020 6:32 PM

To: Nasser Awwad <nsawwad20@yahoo.com>

Cc: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>

Subject: Re: IntechOpen - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

Dear Dr. Anowar,

Thank you for your kind words.

We are currently waiting for a couple chapters to be finalized. One authors needs to send a revision and two others need to submit a chapter for review.

Also, Prof. Samanta's chapter is currently under review with an external reviewer and I will be sending the results soon.

I hope that the book will be ready for final processing in the upcoming month.

Kind regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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Rijeka: Janeza Trdine 9, 51000 Rijeka, Croatia

London: 10 Lower Thames Street, London, EC3R 6AF, UK

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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On 13. 02. 2020. 13:22, Nasser Awwad wrote:

Dear Mrs Sandra

welcome and happy to be with us as new Author Service Manager for our book project
 "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments. I would ask you about
 , what the current status for this book .

my regards

Nasser Awwad

Nasser S Awwad

Professor of Inorganic and Radiochemistry

Chemistry department, faculty of Science, King Khalid University

Box office # 9004, postal code: 61413, Mobile: 00966549323204 & 00966563764476,

Telephone office: 0172417420

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3477-6996>

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On Thursday, February 13, 2020, 3:09:19 PM GMT+3, Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com> wrote:

Dear Prof. Samanta,

I hope that you are doing well.

I just wanted to reach out and introduce myself as the new Author Service Manager for the book project "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments".

I hope that we will have a successful collaboration and that we will pick up from where you left off without any problems.

Please feel free to contact me in case you have further questions or concerns.

Cordially,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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IntechOpen - Your Chapter Proposal has been Approved - "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments"

- To: me · Thu, Feb 13, 2020 at 6:10 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Following up on my previous email, I would like to confirm that the editor, Prof. Samanta has approved your chapter proposal "A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural Coloration on Natural Fibre."

Below are some suggestions for you to incorporate in your full chapter manuscript:

"This is a very good chapter proposal for practical use to have and present a ready made variety of colored shades with details of recipe and process conditions for few standardized shades using single and mixture of natural colours .

BUt Author should avoid the term or word " Pantone " as it is a registered trade mark for particular company . Hence title should be rtevised as follows : 'A practical guideline of 'few standardized ready made shades of natural dyed textiles " .

It is not understood from abstract how much systematically the matter will be placed . My suggestion is to give Name of the Dye, chemical structure of dye , Name of the Moradant and Filbres concern ,with details of dye extraction , pre -mordanting and dyeing conditions and dyeing process followed for each such shades. Do not give more than 20 such shades and their details. Give an introduction for care and precaution needed for preparation of the fabric before mordanting and natural dyeing and after treatment , if any.

Authors must add all-round of colour fastness data and after treatment to improve it . For each shade, details of cares for tonal variations and estimated colour values like K/s and X, Y and Z values or RGB values must be given for each sahde for on line communication of colour without sending samples.

The chapter proposal may be accepted with incorporation of above matters."

If you have any questions or need any clarification regarding any of our editors suggestions, please let me know.

Page | 116

NEXT STEP: Submit your full chapter (10 to 20 pages) within the next 30 days.

For the preparation of your chapter please use the Templates that can be found by signing in to your Author Panel under the Quick Links section.

To sign in to your Author Panel please use the following link: <https://mts.intechopen.com/booksprocess/action/chapter/211890>

After the full chapter review, you will receive the notification regarding the definitive acceptance of your work in the book.

Let me know if you need any further help.

Cordially,

Sandra Maljavac
Author Service Manager

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18 Cited legal explanation of India and Australia about tax in research project

18.1 Expenditure on scientific research, Income Tax Act, 1961, India

35. (1) In respect of expenditure on scientific research, the following deductions shall be allowed—

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(i) any expenditure (not being in the nature of capital expenditure) laid out or expended on scientific research related to the business.

Explanation.—Where any such expenditure has been laid out or expended before the commencement of the business (not being expenditure laid out or expended before the 1st day of April, 1973) on payment of any salary as defined in Explanation 2 below sub-section (5) of section 40A to an employee engaged in such scientific research or on the purchase of materials used in such scientific research, the aggregate of the expenditure so laid out or expended within the three years immediately preceding the commencement of the business shall, to the extent it is certified by the prescribed authority to have been laid out or expended on such scientific research, be deemed to have been laid out or expended in the previous year in which the business is commenced ;

(ii) an amount equal to one and one half times of any sum paid to a research association which has as its object the undertaking of scientific research or to a university, college or other institution to be used for scientific research:

Provided that such association, university, college or other institution for the purposes of this clause—

(A) is for the time being approved, in accordance with the guidelines, in the manner and subject to such conditions as may be prescribed; and

(B) such association, university, college or other institution is specified as such, by notification in the Official Gazette, by the Central Government:

Provided further that where any sum is paid to such association, university, college or other institution in a previous year relevant to the assessment year beginning on or after the 1st day of April, 2021, the deduction under this clause shall be equal to the sum so paid;

(iia) any sum paid to a company to be used by it for scientific research:

Provided that such company—

(A) is registered in India,

(B) has as its main object the scientific research and development,

(C) is, for the purposes of this clause, for the time being approved by the prescribed authority in the prescribed manner, and

(D) fulfils such other conditions as may be prescribed;

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

(iii) any sum paid to a research association which has as its object the undertaking of research in social science or statistical research or to a university, college or other institution to be used for research in social science or statistical research:

Provided that such association, university, college or other institution for the purposes of this clause—

(A) is for the time being approved, in accordance with the guidelines, in the manner and subject to such conditions as may be prescribed; and

(B) such association, university, college or other institution is specified as such, by notification in the Official Gazette, by the Central Government.

Explanation.—The deduction, to which the assessee is entitled in respect of any sum paid to a research association, university, college or other institution to which clause (ii) or clause (iii) or to a company to which clause (iia) applies, shall not be denied merely on the ground that, subsequent to the payment of such sum by the assessee, the approval granted to the association, university, college or other institution referred to in clause (ii) or clause (iii) or to a company referred to in clause (iia) has been withdrawn;

(iv) in respect of any expenditure of a capital nature on scientific research related to the business carried on by the assessee, such deduction as may be admissible under the provisions of sub-section (2) :

Provided that the research association, university, college or other institution referred to in clause (ii) or clause (iii) shall make an application in the prescribed form and manner to the Central Government for the purpose of grant of approval, or continuance thereof, under clause (ii) or, as the case may be, clause (iii) :

Provided further that the Central Government may, before granting approval under clause (ii) or clause (iii), call for such documents (including audited annual accounts) or information from the research association, university, college or other institution as it thinks necessary in order to satisfy itself about the genuineness of the activities of the research association, university, college or other institution and that Government may also make such inquiries as it may deem necessary in this behalf :

Provided also that any notification issued, by the Central Government under clause (ii) or clause (iii), before the date on which the Taxation Laws (Amendment) Bill, 2006 receives the assent of the President, shall, at any one time, have effect for such assessment year or years, not exceeding

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder, Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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three assessment years (including an assessment year or years commencing before the date on which such notification is issued) as may be specified in the notification:

Provided also that where an application under the first proviso is made on or after the date on which the Taxation Laws (Amendment) Bill, 2006 receives the assent of the President, every notification under clause (ii) or clause (iii) shall be issued or an order rejecting the application shall be passed within the period of twelve months from the end of the month in which such application was received by the Central Government:

Provided also that every notification under clause (ii) or clause (iii) in respect of the research association, university, college or other institution or under clause (iia) in respect of the company issued on or before the date on which this proviso has come into force, shall be deemed to have been withdrawn unless such research association, university, college or other institution referred to in clause (ii) or clause (iii) or the company referred to in clause (iia) makes an intimation in such form and manner, as may be prescribed, to the prescribed income-tax authority within three months from the date on which this proviso has come into force, and subject to such intimation the notification shall be valid for a period of five consecutive assessment years beginning with the assessment year commencing on or after the 1st day of April, 2022:

Provided also that any notification issued by the Central Government under clause (ii) or clause (iia) or clause (iii), after the date on which the Taxation and Other Laws (Relaxation and Amendment of Certain Provisions) Bill, 2020 receives the assent of the President, shall, at any one time, have effect for such assessment year or years, not exceeding five assessment years as may be specified in the notification.

(1A) Notwithstanding anything contained in sub-section (1), the deduction in respect of any sum paid to the research association, university, college or other institution referred to in clause (ii) or clause (iii), or the company referred to in clause (iia) of sub-section (1), shall not be allowed, unless such research association, university, college or other institution or company—

- i) prepares such statement for such period as may be prescribed and deliver or cause to be delivered to the said prescribed income-tax authority or the person authorised by such authority such statement in such form, verified in such manner, setting forth such particulars and within such time, as may be prescribed:

Provided that such research association, university, college or other institution or the company may also deliver to the prescribed authority a correction statement for rectification of any mistake or to add, delete or update the information furnished in the statement delivered under this sub-section in such form and verified in such manner as may be prescribed;

(ii) furnishes to the donor, a certificate specifying the amount of donation in such manner, containing such particulars and within such time from the date of receipt of sum, as may be prescribed.

(2) For the purposes of clause (iv) of sub-section (1),

(i) in a case where such capital expenditure is incurred before the 1st day of April, 1967, one-fifth of the capital expenditure incurred in any previous year shall be deducted for that previous year; and the balance of the expenditure shall be deducted in equal instalments for each of the four immediately succeeding previous years;

(ia) in a case where such capital expenditure is incurred after the 31st day of March, 1967, the whole of such capital expenditure incurred in any previous year shall be deducted for that previous year:

Provided that no deduction shall be admissible under this clause in respect of any expenditure incurred on the acquisition of any land, whether the land is acquired as such or as part of any property, after the 29th day of February, 1984.

Explanation 1. Where any capital expenditure has been incurred before the commencement of the business, the aggregate of the expenditure so incurred within the three years immediately preceding the commencement of the business shall be deemed to have been incurred in the previous year in which the business is commenced.

Explanation 2. For the purposes of this clause,

(a) "land" includes any interest in land ; and

(b) the acquisition of any land shall be deemed to have been made by the assessee on the date on which the instrument of transfer of such land to him has been registered under the Registration Act, 1908 (16 of 1908), or where he has taken or retained the possession of such land or any part thereof in part performance of a contract of the nature referred to in section 53A of the Transfer of Property Act, 1882 (4 of 1882), the date on which he has so taken or retained possession of such land or part ;

(ii) notwithstanding anything contained in clause (i), where an asset representing expenditure of a capital nature incurred before the 1st day of April, 1967, ceases to be used in a previous year for scientific research related to the business and the value of the asset at the time of the cessation, together with the aggregate of deductions already allowed under clause (i) falls short of the said expenditure, then—

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- (a) there shall be allowed a deduction for that previous year of an amount equal to such deficiency, and
- (b) no deduction shall be allowed under that clause for that previous year or for any subsequent previous year;
- (iii) if the asset mentioned in clause (ii) is sold, without having been used for other purposes, in the year of cessation, the sale price shall be taken to be the value of the asset at the time of the cessation ; and if the asset is sold, without having been used for other purposes, in a previous year subsequent to the year of cessation, and the sale price falls short of the value of the asset taken into account at the time of cessation, an amount equal to the deficiency shall be allowed as a deduction for the previous year in which the sale took place;
- (iv) where a deduction is allowed for any previous year under this section in respect of expenditure represented wholly or partly by an asset, no deduction shall be allowed under clause (ii) of sub-section (1) of section 32 for the same or any other previous year in respect of that asset;
- (v) where the asset mentioned in clause (ii) is used in the business after it ceases to be used for scientific research related to that business, depreciation shall be admissible under clause (ii) of sub-section (1) of section 32.

(2A) Where, before the 1st day of March, 1984, the assessee pays any sum (being any sum paid with a specific direction that the sum shall not be used for the acquisition of any land or building or construction of any building) to a scientific research association or university or college or other institution referred to in clause (ii) of sub-section (1) or to a public sector company to be used for scientific research undertaken under a programme approved in this behalf by the prescribed authority having regard to the social, economic and industrial needs of India, then,—

- (a) there shall be allowed a deduction of a sum equal to one and one-third times the sum so paid ; and
- (b) no deduction in respect of such sum shall be allowed under clause (ii) of sub-section (1) for the same or any other assessment year.

Explanation.—For the purposes of this sub-section, "public sector company" shall have the same meaning as in clause (b) of the Explanation below sub-section (2B) of section 32A.

(2AA) Where the assessee pays any sum to a National Laboratory or a University or an Indian Institute of Technology or a specified person with a specific direction that the said sum shall be

used for scientific research undertaken under a programme approved in this behalf by the prescribed authority, then—

(a) there shall be allowed a deduction of a sum equal to one and one-half times the sum so paid; and

(b) no deduction in respect of such sum shall be allowed under any other provision of this Act:

Provided that the prescribed authority shall, before granting approval, satisfy itself about the feasibility of carrying out the scientific research and shall submit its report to the Principal Chief Commissioner or Chief Commissioner or Principal Director General or Director General in such form as may be prescribed:

Provided further that where any sum is paid to such National Laboratory or university or Indian Institute of Technology or specified person in a previous year relevant to the assessment year beginning on or after the 1st day of April, 2021, the deduction under this sub-section shall be equal to the sum so paid.

Explanation 1.—The deduction, to which the assessee is entitled in respect of any sum paid to a National Laboratory, University, Indian Institute of Technology or a specified person for the approved programme referred to in this sub-section, shall not be denied merely on the ground that, subsequent to the payment of such sum by the assessee, the approval granted to,—

(a) such Laboratory, or specified person has been withdrawn; or

(b) the programme, undertaken by the National Laboratory, University, Indian Institute of Technology or specified person, has been withdrawn.

Explanation 2.—For the purposes of this section,—

(a) "National Laboratory" means a scientific laboratory functioning at the national level under the aegis of the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, the Indian Council of Medical Research, the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, the Defence Research and Development Organisation, the Department of Electronics, the Department of Bio-Technology or the Department of Atomic Energy and which is approved as a National Laboratory by the prescribed authority in such manner as may be prescribed ;

(b) "University" shall have the same meaning as in Explanation to clause (ix) of section 47 ;

(c) "Indian Institute of Technology" shall have the same meaning as that of "Institute" in clause (g) of section 3 of the Institutes of Technology Act, 1961 (59 of 1961);

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(d) "specified person" means such person as is approved by the prescribed authority.

(2AB)(1) Where a company engaged in the business of bio-technology or in any business of manufacture or production of any article or thing, not being an article or thing specified in the list of the Eleventh Schedule incurs any expenditure on scientific research (not being expenditure in the nature of cost of any land or building) on in-house research and development facility as approved by the prescribed authority, then, there shall be allowed a deduction of a sum equal to one and one-half times of the expenditure so incurred:

Provided that where such expenditure on scientific research (not being expenditure in the nature of cost of any land or building) on in-house research and development facility is incurred in a previous year relevant to the assessment year beginning on or after the 1st day of April, 2021, the deduction under this clause shall be equal to the expenditure so incurred.

Explanation.—For the purposes of this clause, "expenditure on scientific research", in relation to drugs and pharmaceuticals, shall include expenditure incurred on clinical drug trial, obtaining approval from any regulatory authority under any Central, State or Provincial Act and filing an application for a patent under the Patents Act, 1970 (39 of 1970).

(2) No deduction shall be allowed in respect of the expenditure mentioned in clause (1) under any other provision of this Act.

(3) No company shall be entitled for deduction under clause (1) unless it enters into an agreement with the prescribed authority for co-operation in such research and development facility and fulfils such conditions with regard to maintenance of accounts and audit thereof and furnishing of reports in such manner as may be prescribed.

(4) The prescribed authority shall submit its report in relation to the approval of the said facility to the Principal Chief Commissioner or Chief Commissioner or Principal Director General or Director General in such form and within such time as may be prescribed.

(5) [***]

(6) No deduction shall be allowed to a company approved under sub-clause (C) of clause (ia) of sub-section (1) in respect of the expenditure referred to in clause (1) which is incurred after the 31st day of March, 2008.

(2B)(a) Where, before the 1st day of March, 1984, an asses see has incurred any expenditure (not being in the nature of capital expenditure incurred on the acquisition of any land or building or construction of any building) on scientific research undertaken under a programme approved in this behalf by the pre scribed authority having regard to the social, economic and industrial needs

of India, he shall, subject to the provisions of this sub-section, be allowed a deduction of a sum equal to one and one-fourth times the amount of the expenditure certified by the prescribed authority to have been so incurred during the previous year.

(b) Where a deduction has been allowed under clause (a) for any previous year in respect of any expenditure, no deduction in respect of such expenditure shall be allowed under clause (i) of sub-section (1) or clause (ia) of sub-section (2) for the same or any other previous year.

(c) Where a deduction is allowed for any previous year under this sub-section in respect of expenditure represented wholly or partly by an asset, no deduction shall be allowed in respect of that asset under clause (ii) of sub-section (1) of section 32 for the same or any subsequent previous year.

(d) Any deduction made under this sub-section in respect of any expenditure on scientific research in excess of the expenditure actually incurred shall be deemed to have been wrongly made for the purposes of this Act if the assessee fails to furnish within one year of the period allowed by the prescribed authority for completion of the programme, a certificate of its completion obtained from that authority, and the provisions of sub-section (5B) of section 155 shall apply accordingly.

(3) If any question arises under this section as to whether, and if so, to what extent, any activity constitutes or constituted, or any asset is or was being used for, scientific research, the Board shall refer the question to—

(a) the Central Government, when such question relates to any activity under clauses (ii) and (iii) of sub-section (1), and its decision shall be final;

(b) the prescribed authority, when such question relates to any activity other than the activity specified in clause (a), whose decision shall be final.

(4) The provisions of sub-section (2) of section 32 shall apply in relation to deductions allowable under clause (iv) of sub-section (1) as they apply in relation to deductions allowable in respect of depreciation.

(5) Where, in a scheme of amalgamation, the amalgamating company sells or otherwise transfers to the amalgamated company (being an Indian company) any asset representing expenditure of a capital nature on scientific research,—

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(i) the amalgamating company shall not be allowed the deduction under clause (ii) or clause (iii) of sub-section (2); and

(ii) the provisions of this section shall, as far as may be, apply to the amalgamated company as they would have applied to the amalgamating company if the latter had not so sold or otherwise transferred the asset.

18.2 Expenditure on scientific research, income tax assessment act 1936, section 73A, Australia

(1A) This section has effect subject to Division 245 of the [Income Tax Assessment Act 1997](#) .

(1) The following payments made, and expenditure incurred, during the [year of income](#) (other than any amount which is allowable as a deduction under any other section of [this Act](#)) by a [person](#) carrying on a [business](#) for the purpose of gaining or producing [assessable income](#) shall be [allowable deductions](#):

(a) Payments to:

- (i) [an approved research institute](#) for [scientific research](#) related to that [business](#); or
- (ii) [an approved research institute](#), the object of which is the undertaking of [scientific research](#) related to the class of [business](#) to which that [business](#) belongs; and

(b) Expenditure of a capital nature on [scientific research](#) related to that [business](#) (except to the extent that it is expenditure on plant, machinery, land or buildings or on alterations, additions or extensions to buildings or in the acquisition of rights in or arising out of [scientific research](#)).

(2) Where, on or after the first day of the [year of income](#) ending on 30 June 1946, a [taxpayer](#) carrying on a [business](#) for the purpose of gaining or producing [assessable income](#) incurs expenditure of a capital nature in the construction or acquisition of a building, or part of a building, or in making any alteration or addition to a building, in which [scientific research](#) related to that [business](#) is to be carried on by or on behalf of the [taxpayer](#), and the building, part of a building, alteration or addition, as the case

may be, is of use for [scientific research](#) purposes only, an amount equal to one - third of that expenditure shall be an [allowable deduction](#):

(a) from the [assessable income](#) of the [year of income](#) in which the building, part of a building, alteration or addition is first used by or on behalf of the [taxpayer](#) for such [scientific research](#); and

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(b) from the [assessable income](#) of each of the 2 years of income next succeeding that [year of income](#), if the [taxpayer](#) continues to carry on that [business](#) during the year in which that [assessable income](#) was derived.

(2A) [Subsection](#) (2) does not apply to expenditure incurred by a [taxpayer](#) in the construction of a building or part of a building, in the making of an alteration or addition to a building or in the acquisition of a building or part of a building unless:

(a) either of the following subparagraphs applies:

(i) that construction or making commenced, or that acquisition occurred, before 21 November 1987;

(ii) any contract in respect of that construction, making or acquisition was entered into before 21 November 1987; and

(b) if the expenditure was incurred after 20 November 1987--the [taxpayer](#) intended, on 20 November 1987, that:

(i) [scientific research](#), being research related to a [business](#) carried on by the [taxpayer](#) for the purpose of gaining or producing [assessable income](#), would be carried on by or on behalf of the [taxpayer](#) in the building; and

(ii) the building, part of the building, alteration or addition, as the case may be, would be of use for [scientific research](#) purposes only.

(3) Where any expenditure or payment to which this section refers is incurred or made outside [Australia](#) and the [business](#) in relation to which it is so incurred or made is carried on partly in and partly out of [Australia](#), the deduction allowable under this

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section shall be such part of the amount which would otherwise be allowable as the [Commissioner](#) considers reasonable in the circumstances.

(4) Where any expenditure has been allowed or is allowable as a deduction under [subsection \(2\)](#) and:

- (a) the [taxpayer](#) sells, [transfers](#) or otherwise disposes of the building or any part thereof; or
- (b) the building or any part thereof is destroyed;

the [termination value](#) of the building or part shall, to the extent of the expenditure so allowed or allowable as a deduction, be included in the [assessable income](#) of the [year of income](#) in which the disposal or destruction occurs:

[Provided](#) that where the [Commissioner](#) is of opinion that part only, or no part, of that [termination value](#) relates to the disposal or destruction of any [property](#) which was acquired or created by that expenditure, that part only, or no part, as the case may be, of the [termination value](#) shall be taken into account for the purposes of this [subsection](#).

(4A) If:

(a) a [person](#) has purchased from another [person](#) a building, or part of a building, where the vendor had incurred capital expenditure of a kind in respect of which deductions are or have been allowable under [subsection \(2\)](#); and

(b) it would be concluded that, having regard to any connection between the vendor and the purchaser or to any other [relevant circumstances](#), those [persons](#) were not dealing with each other at arm's length; and

(c) the purchase price is greater or lesser than the market value of the building, or the part of the building, at the time of the purchase;

the purchase price is, for all purposes of the application of [this Act](#) in relation to the vendor, taken to have been the amount of the market value of the [property](#) at the time of the purchase.

(5) If the purchase of the building is a [creditable acquisition](#) by the vendor, references in [subsection](#) (4A) to the purchase price are taken to be references to that price reduced by the amount of the [net input tax credit](#) to which the purchaser is entitled for the acquisition.

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(6) In this section:

"an approved research institute" means the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organization, or any university, college, institute, association or organization which is approved in writing for the purposes of this section by that Organization, by the Chief Executive Officer of the [NHMRC](#) or by the [Research Secretary](#), as an institution, association or organization for undertaking [scientific research](#) which is or may prove to be of value to [Australia](#).

"NHMRC" means the National Health and Medical Research Council established by section [5B](#) of the [National Health and Medical Research Council Act 1992](#) .

"Research Secretary" means the Secretary of the Department administered by the Minister administering the [Australian Research Council Act 2001](#) .

"scientific research" means any activities in the fields of natural or applied science for the extension of knowledge.

"termination value" has the meaning given by [subsection](#) 995 - 1(1) of the [Income Tax Assessment Act 1997](#) .

(7) An approval for the purposes of [subsection](#) (6) may:

(a) operate as from a date, whether before or after the date of the approval, specified in the instrument of approval; and

(b) be withdrawn at any time.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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(8) In this section, any reference to scientific research related to a business or class of business shall be read as including a reference to:

(i) any scientific research which may lead to or facilitate an extension, or an improvement in the technical efficiency, of that business, or, as the case may be, of businesses of that class; and

(ii) any scientific research of a medical nature which is of special relation to the welfare of workers employed in that business or, as the case may be, in businesses of that class.

(9) This section does not apply in relation to payments made, or expenditure incurred, after 30 June 1995.

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

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Hossain, M. A. (2023bd). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02)*.

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Hossain, M. A. (2023bf). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-04)*.

[http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27336.08962;](http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27336.08962) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8047201>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-05)*.

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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder, Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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on 18 April 2023, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844597>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28176.28165>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747607>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116196>

Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10182345>

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29042.48322>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048>

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Hossain, M. A. (2023bt). *Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist.* <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34177.43368>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208384>

Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-*

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>;

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12742364>

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195451>

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Hossain, M. A. (2023by). *Reporting to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship.* . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>

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- Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cf). *A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12722555>
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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cl). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02).*

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Hossain, M. A. (2024b). *Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government.*

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>

Hossain, M. A. (2024c). *Coalesced the syllabus and course structures in textile engineering and relevant courses in the eighteen years duration academic and professional journey of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist from 2006 to 2024.*

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>;

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Hossain, M. A. (2024f). *Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of “Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist” on “Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds” School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).*

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>

Hossain, M. A. (2024i). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>

Hossain, M. A. (2024j). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>

Hossain, M. A. (2024k). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Hossain, M. A. (2024l). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>

Hossain, M. A. (2024m). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>

Hossain, M. A. (2024n). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent*

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder, Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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residence visa (subclass 858) under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560>;

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Hossain, M. A. (2024o). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Hossain, M. A. (2024p). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Hossain, M. A. (2024q). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>

Hossain, M. A. (2024r). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325>;

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Hossain, M. A. (2024s). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282>;

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Hossain, M. A. (2024t). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16628548>

Hossain, M. A. (2024u). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Hossain, M. A. (2024v). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an*

- international standard University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024w). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>
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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre*; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre

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Abstract

Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing can be established by developing completely eco-friendly natural dyes and natural finishing agent which can be applied on cotton textiles (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a newer technique of simultaneous Mordanting-Dyeing-Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process time, processing costs and effluent load as well as to develop the single step processes and also completely eco-friendly products of cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from an extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy. There is huge scope of commercialization of such Oeko-Tech (Eco-Friendly) products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile products for domestic and export market. Different selective natural dyes like teak leaf, turmeric, jackfruit wood, sappan wood, skin of onion, arjuna bark etc., bio-mordanting agent like bio-enzyme, harda, lemon as natural mordanting agents, extracted soyabean seed as natural chemical modification as well as natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent where all dyed and finished fabric can be scientifically tested by SEM, FTIR, DSC, HPLC, GCMS, TLC, CHNS, X-ray diffraction pattern etc.

Introduction

Worldwide growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products is generating more and more customer's interests on natural fibres based textile as well as on natural dyes and natural finishing, particularly for the Export market. Considering this corner, textile sector has the highest scope to apply this research work for attracting the value-added customer. But, till today there is a huge lack of research and development of natural dyeing and finishing based textile product. There are ample scopes of doing scientific research on the application of natural dyes on cotton and other textiles aimed at obtaining newer shade with acceptable colour fastness behaviour and uniform and reproducible colour yield through appropriate techniques. Simultaneous natural dyeing and natural finishing: a new technique will thus serve process steps like energy and total process cost. Reducing process cost will minimize total cost of the product in the export market, it will be highly beneficial

to sustain in a competitive market if the expected research output can be applied successfully in Government and non-government textile mill at home and abroad.

Cotton is still a natural fibre of agro-origin that is used most in the world. About 46% of all fibre produced in the world is cotton. Even today cotton is the backbone of the world's textile trade. The cotton fibre presents many exceptional features like great flexibility, cohesive property, very small thickness, but high strength and wear resistance. Owing to these properties it is possible to process cotton fibres into yarns with greater diversity; from thick yarn for manufacturing coarse and different upholstery/furnishing as well as denim type apparel fabrics to very fine yarns for manufacturing thin and refined fabrics such as Batiste, Marquisette, Muslin, etc. Cotton fibre is widely used for making all types of apparels as well as all types of furnishing fabrics. In textile applications this biodegradable, environment-friendly and renewable fibre has some

distinct advantages such as moderate dry and wet tensile strength, appreciable moisture regains, agreeable feel, moderate extensibility, varied dye ability and appreciable UV-light stability. However, the major disadvantages of cotton lie in its dimensional instability as revealed by wash shrinkage, poor wrinkle recovery and ready susceptibility to microbial degradation.

Natural dyes are considered to be eco-friendly as these are obtained from renewable resources as compared to synthetic dyes which are derived from non-renewable petroleum resources. These are biodegradable and the residual vegetal matter left after extraction of dyes can be easily composted and used as fertilizer. They produce soft colours soothing to the eye which is in harmony with nature which is gradually gaining popularity due to its non-toxicity and eco-friendly character against possible unsafe ecotoxicity criteria of synthetic dyes. Most of the studies available for dyeing with natural dyes relates to cotton textiles and such studies on cotton are still insufficient to establish. Hence, there are ample scope of undertaking an integrated study in this area for cotton and chemically modified cotton to study its surface appearance, durability and dyeing of cotton and chemically modified cotton with natural dyes.

Literature Review

Growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products has caused more interest on cotton fibre based natural dyeing and finishing. Productions of synthetic dyes are dependent on the petrochemical source and some of the synthetic dyes contain toxic/carcinogenic amines and are not eco-friendly. Contrary to this, most of the natural dyes as well as natural finish with few exceptions are based on vegetable/ animal origin and are renewable, biodegradable, energy-efficient and eco-friendly[1,2]. The most important issue now is origin and classification of some natural dyes applicable for different fibres are available in the literature [3-5]. Gupta, et al. [6] have documented some of the traditional processes of application of some natural dyes. Kawahito, et al. [7] have compared the dyeing of cellulosic fabric with natural indigo and synthetic indigo. Radhakrishnan[8] as well as Ajita, et al.[9] have reported the effect of different mordants on selective natural dyes. Grierson, et al. [10] has studied colour fastness characteristics of some natural dyes. Lee, et al. [11] have studied the colour fastness properties of some natural dyes by applying UV-absorbers. Effect of chemical structure on light fastness property of some natural dyes has been reported by Gupta, et al. [12]. Oda, et al. [13] has studied the effect of phenyl ester functional group on photofading of carthamin on cellulose acetate. Most of the studies are sporadic and insufficient in developing scientific knowledge base on the subject. Therefore, very less study on simultaneous natural dyeing and finishing, dyeing process variables and characterisation etc. Hence, an integrated scientific study for selective natural dye-fibre system, for selective natural dyes applied on cotton and other textiles is felt necessary, for establishing the process optimization in naturally dyed textiles. [14, 15 16, 17] Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural fin-

ishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing were experimented in earlier research on natural coloration.

Application of Different Biomordanting with Biomordanting Agents

Effects of different degrees of biomordanting like bioenzyme, harda and lemon as natural mordanting agents and natural chemical modification extracted from soyabean seed on cotton fabric for altering its textile related properties and dye ability with selective natural dyes (say a teak leaf, turmeric, Jackfruit wood, sappan wood etc.) can be investigated. Effect of such biomodifications on colour parameters after dyeing of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified cotton and its colour fastness properties to light, washing, perspiration and rubbing can be studied. The photo fading behaviour of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified and dyed cotton materials after those modifications and pre-treatments and subsequent dyeing can be studied and an attempt can be taken to improve the same to a much better level of customer acceptability. Effects of different degree of chemical modifications on colour yield for the selective natural dyes can be studied. Cotton Textile materials dyed with natural dyes can be post-treated/finished with suitable natural agents for studying the effect of these after treatments on the improvement of colour yield, brightness and colour fastness behaviour of the dyed material. To improve the colour fastness properties for the selective natural dyes some pre or post-treatment with cationic or metallic complex compound or UV absorbers/suitable modifiers can be studied.

Process Development

The fabrics can be pre-treated by the eco-friendly enzyme-based chemical pre-treatment processes for preparing it for simultaneous dyeing and finishing. After that different natural dyes (say teak leaf, turmeric, jackfruit wood, sappan wood etc.) as well as natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent can be applied on cotton fabric for trailing and experimentations on application of dyes and finishing agent on cotton and optimization of dyeing process variables for improved colour development and improvement of colour fastness, all analytical testing. Effects of variations of dyeing process variables on colour yield and dyeing kinetics for application of selective natural dyes on cotton and chemically modified cotton substrate can be investigated to understand the dyeing isotherm, rate of dyeing and other thermodynamic parameters for such dyeing. This will help to understand the dyeing behaviours of different natural dyes applied on cotton to get an idea of formulating better colour yield having specific standardized dyeing recipe for combined/compound shades by use of binary or ternary mixture of these natural dyes. For use of combination of natural dyes for generating compound shades, a study on the compatibility of such binary and a ternary mixture of dyes can be also studied, to understand and find a compatible combination of such dyes for cotton

and chemically treated and modified cotton fabrics.

Process of Textile Properties and Dyeability Analysis

Changes in structural features for different degrees of chemical modifications (enzymatic hydrolysis, oxidation on cotton substrate can be investigated with the help of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), FTIR Spectroscopy and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), High-Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPLC), Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GCMS), Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC), Carbon, Hydrogen, Nitrogen and Sulphur (CHNS) analyzer and X-ray diffraction pattern etc. for explaining the major observations in these aspects. This will help to understand scientifically the scientific analysis of different changes in textile related property behaviour and dyeability in terms of changes in structural features of chemically modified cotton substrate along with changes in surface characteristics and durability etc.

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A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles

Anowar Hossain

Abstract

Marigold flower *Tagetes erecta* L., Arjuna Bark *Terminalia Arjuna*, Eucalyptus leaves *Eucalyptus Radiata*, Peach/Jam Leaves *Acacia acuminata*, Pecker leaves *Cinnamomum tamala*, Guava leaves *Psidium guajava*, Basil leaves *Ocimum basilicum*, Jackfruit wood *Artocarpus heterophyllus*, Catachu fruit *Senegalia Catechu*, Bohera fruit *Terminalia bellirica*, Betel nut fruit *Areca catechu*, Haritaki fruit *Terminalia chebula*, Mahogany fruit peel, Mahogany seed peel, and Mahogany seed *Swietenia macrophylla* are the common natural sources in Bangladesh, an Asian country which were experimented in terms of mordanting free natural coloration on cotton fabric under conceptual confirmation of referred journal where author has been picked the idea from the generation of available shade in his research laboratory and tested from different laboratories and it may be establish as mordant free natural dyeing for specific colorant on the basis of color fastness and shading behaviors. Fifteen standardized Ready Made Shade (RMS) has been presented with CIE color parameters, color fastness, wash fastness, and light fastness grading. A reproducing guideline for every Ready Made Shade (RMS) has been mentioned in this chapter.

Keywords: readymade shade (RMS), natural dyeing, eco-friendly dyes, natural extraction, mordant free dyeing

1. Introduction

A concept of readymade shade (RMS) has been developed by using numerous number of natural dyes which were collected from agri-production unit and different village sources in Bangladesh prepared and powdered in color processing unit, extracted with water solvent process, dyed and experimented the feasibility of coloration in textile chemistry laboratory to generate different hues of natural dyes after effective implementation on natural fiber based textiles which outcome of color may be beneficial for primary selection of color tone by the textile technologist of natural coloration cum customers for the decision-making of specific color tone both for product development and fashion concerns who are genuinely searching an eco-friendly dyes under the consideration of repeated hue without which the real output of natural coloration, sustainability of dyes and natural dyeing process as well as its actual production of different hue is being a challenged now as the textile technologists are habituated the essence of readymade shading behavior of synthetic dyes whereas toxicity is the main endangered for the human being.

2. Background

Environment pollution is the great challenge of color scientists in dyeing and finishing plant, so eco-friendly coloration is the key target of recent researchers and manufacturers. Natural coloration is being accepted by the environment scientist and related committee [1–3]. Researchers in the area of natural coloration have an immense intension to minimize pollution [4]. Focus on science and engineering on natural dyes based research, extractions, purifications, and implementations are rapidly climbing [5–9]. In this chapter, mordant free natural coloration and its feasibility was experimented to minimize environment pollution load which is not limited to synthetic dyeing but also natural dyeing in terms of mordant free coloration concepts for specific standardized shade. Author also experimented to establish an approach of green mordanting [10, 11] in natural coloration [12–16] although mordant [17] has an effect for the augmentation of fiber surface color and surface chemistry [18] and its appropriate affinity in terms of fastness properties [1, 19–24]. Light fastness [21–24] of natural dyed fabric is a critical issue for natural colorant if dyes sources and collection processes are not maintained accurately. There are many sources of natural colorant, using by the researcher as per availability of origin to origin in the world. Researchers are already invented and proposed like *Jatropha* flower [25], red sandal wood [26], wood of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* [27], *Acalypha* [28], areca nut [29], *Butea monosperma* [30], neem leaves [31, 32], *Gomphrena globosa* [33], *Onosmaechiodes* [34], *Nerium oleander* flower [35], Kesula flowers [36], Parijataka (*Nyctanthes Arbor*) flowers pigment [37], *Hibiscus ovalifolius* and *Sesbania aegyptiaca* [38], Bark of *Macaranga Peltata* [39], Cutch, Ratanjot and Madder [40], Mesta Calyx [41], Kapila, Onion, Tesu [42], myrobalan, gallnut, pomegranate [43], Marigold flower [44, 45], *Areca Catechu* [46], Eucalyptus leaves [47], Eucalyptus bark [48, 49], Jackfruit wood [50], Peach [51], Arjuna [52, 53], *Catechu* [54] and others. Developments of natural indigo shade in comparison with synthetic dyes [55] are not only prime objects for coloration but also maximum natural dyes have medicinal value [56, 57], noncarcinogenic, production-friendly, and environment-friendly. Research and development of natural dyeing on cotton, jute, and silk fabric was done by Samanta and his researchers team at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India have an technical output, research impacts and motivation for future researchers, and manufacturing unit for the contributions of dyes selection, extraction, analysis, standardization, and commercialization [58–68]. Color matching [69] and reproducing of shade is another challenging issue for the manufacturing company and colorists when natural dye is compared with synthetic dyes but there are so many colorants of natural sources that can be possible to reproduce almost nearest shade. Tolerating percentage/ acceptable range of color differences, ΔE value, and other properties can be standardized in a convincing way with local and foreign customer of any country as the real customer of any textile product is not going to sell the product after shade matching with spectrophotometer without enjoying its esthetic value, so a little bit lightness and darkness matter is not a trading challenge of dyer and manufacturing plant. Comparing to synthetic dyes, natural dyed fabric has a great market demand as the people who are concern about the intimidation of environment. Thus natural dyes have diverse applications and multi fiber based production options that are already available in literature for cotton [68], jute [66], wool [70], silk [34] based dyeing, processing in both laboratory stage and bulk production (**Figures 1–15**).

RMS of Marigold (Figure 1): Waste Marigold flowers were collected from flower garden, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

3. Standardized Ready Made Shade (RMS) of natural dyed textiles

3.1 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Marigold flower, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Marigold tree. scientific name: *Tagetes erecta*

Figure 1.
 RMS of Marigold.

3.2 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Arjuna Bark, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Arjuna tree, Scientific name: *Terminalia arjuna*

Figure 2.
 RMS of Arjuna Bark.

3.3 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Eucalyptus leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: scientific name: *Eucalyptus radiata*

Figure 3.
RMS of *Eucalyptus* leaves.

Coloring components Zeaxanthin and Lutein structural group of marigold flower may be responsible for good color combination has OH group may be showed good color fastness properties with cellulosic fiber. Lutein (C₄₀H₅₆O₂) and Zeaxanthin (C₄₀H₅₆O₂) molecules may prevent UV damage for its strong antioxidant properties.

RMS of Arjuna Bark (Figure 2): Dried Arjuna bark were plucked from Arjuna tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Ferrous ion of Arjuna Bark may be influencing the L*, a*, b*, Y value for providing outcome of deeper color and OH group is responsible for good fastness properties. Arjuna bark has phytosterol, lactones, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and tannins, glycosides where tannin may be responsible for coloring agent.

RMS of Eucalyptus Leaves (Figure 3): Semi-dried leaves were plucked from Eucalyptus tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group of cellulose can easily make a bonding with dyes group of Eucalyptus. Eucalyptol is a colorless compound which is responsible for antibacterial properties but may be remaining pigment or other phytochemical compound is making color on the fabric surface.

3.4 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Pecker leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Pecker tree, scientific name: *Cinnamomum tamala*

Figure 4.
RMS of Pecker leaves.

RMS of Pecker Leaves (Figure 4): Semi-dried leaves were plucked from pecker tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group of cellulose can easily make a bonding with dyes group of Pecker leaves. Eugenol is the main constituent of antimicrobial properties and other components like pinene, camphene, and limousine may be responsible for color formation.

RMS of Guava Leaves (Figure 5): Semi-dried leaves were plucked from tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group of dyes is responsible for good color fastness properties. Mixed components of flavonoid and tannin are highly responsible for bluish color of cotton fabric. Acidic pH and phenolic compound of guava leaves may generate flammable characteristics of guava leaves colored fabric.

RMS of Basil Leaves (Figure 6): Fresh and green Basil leaves were plucked from tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

α terpineol remaining in dyes of Basil leaves may be responsible for dyeing of cotton fiber and OH group is making strong affinity with cellulose. Phytochemical constituents and medicinal properties of Tulsi leaves may create pathogen protective finish of cotton fabric like antimicrobial, COVID 19, and other viruses.

3.5 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Guava leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Guava tree, scientific name: *Psidium guajava*

Figure 5.
RMS of Guava leaves.

3.6 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Basil leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Basil tree, scientific name: *Ocimum basilicum*

Figure 6.
RMS of Basil leaves.

3.7 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Jackfruit wood, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Jackfruit tree, scientific name: *Artocarpus heterophyllus*

Figure 7.
 RMS of Jackfruit wood.

3.8 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Catechu fruit peel, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Catechu tree, scientific name: *Senegalia catechu*

Figure 8.
 RMS of Catachu fruit.

3.9 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Bohera fruit peel, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Bohera tree, scientific name: *Terminalia bellirica*

Figure 9.
RMS of Bohera fruit.

RMS of Jackfruit Wood (Figure 7): Powder of Jackfruit wood were collected from saw mill, filtered and 5 days dried with summer sun light. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Artocarpesin and Norartocarpetin group of golden yellow color jackfruit tree wood has phenolic compounds, apigenin, curcumin may be responsible for making a yellow color having an optimum value of L^* , a^* , b^* , Y as well as OH group is improving color fastness properties.

RMS of Catachu Fruit (Figure 8): Semidried Catachu fruit were plucked from tree, washed, fruit peel were cut into small piece, 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Catachu is making off white color with soft hand feel and may be remaining natural pigment in the chemical components is responsible for dyeing without mordanting. Coloring component in the catechu is catechin having molecular formula $C_{15}H_{14}O_6$.

RMS of Bohera Fruit (Figure 9): Bohera fruit powder was purchased from herbal medicine shop, Tongi, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

3.10 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Mahogany seed, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Mahogany tree, scientific name: *Swietenia macrophylla*

Figure 10.
 RMS of Mahogany fruit, seed.

3.11 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Mahogany fruit (outer peel), types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Mahogany tree, scientific name: *Swietenia macrophylla*

Figure 11.
 RMS of Mahogany fruit, outer peel.

3.12 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Mahogany seed (outer peel), types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Mahogany tree, scientific name: *Swietenia macrophylla*

Figure 12.
RMS of Mahogany fruit, outer peel of seed.

OH group and its tannin constituent may be created a natural shading environment on the surface of cotton fiber and its medicinal properties may create the dyed fabric antimicrobial. Flavonoid and falfvins constituent of Bohera fruit may have adaptive capabilities of viruses and microorganisms.

RMS of Mahogany Fruit, Seed (Figure 10): Semi-ripped Mahogany fruits were plucked from tree, washed, seeds were separated with sharp knife, cut into small pieces and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group may be responsible for good dye-absorption and ferrous ion may be responsible for dyeing. Phytochemical constituents and other medicinal properties may have a good source protective clothing like insect repellent, antimicrobial, COVID19, and other viruses.

3.13 Natural coloration of cotton natural coloration of cotton fabric with Haritaki fruit peel, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Haritaki tree, scientific name: *Terminalia chebula*

Figure 13.
RMS of Haritaki fruit.

3.14 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Betel nut, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Betel nut tree, scientific name: *Areca catechu*

Figure 14.
RMS of Betel nut.

3.15 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Peach leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Peach leaves, scientific name: *Acacia acuminata*

Figure 15.
RMS of Peach leaves.

RMS of Mahogany Fruit, Outer peel (Figure 11): Semi-ripped Mahogany fruit were plucked from tree, washed, fruit peels were separated with sharp knife, cut into small pieces and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group and ferrous ion may be responsible for good dye-fiber bonding phytochemical constituents and other medicinal properties may have a good source protective clothing like insect repellent, antimicrobial, COVID19, and other viruses.

RMS of Mahogany Fruit, Outer peel of Seed (Figure 12): Semi-ripped Mahogany fruit were plucked from tree, washed, seed peels were separated with sharp knife, cut into small pieces and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group and ferrous ion may be responsible for good dye-fiber bonding. Phytochemical constituents and other medicinal properties may have a good source protective clothing like insect repellent, antimicrobial, COVID19, and other viruses.

RMS of Haritaki Fruit (Figure 13): Haritaki fruit powder was purchased from herbal medicine shop Tongi, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group and ferrous ion may be responsible for good dye-fiber bonding. The plant is constituted of Glucoside, Tannins, Gallic acid, Ethyl gallate, and Chebulinic acid where tannin may be responsible for coloring the cotton fiber.

RMS of Betel Nut (Figure 14): Ripe Betel nut were purchased from local village shop, separated the peels, and grinded to make it powder form. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group can create a bond between dye and fiber and remaining curcumin may be responsible for coloration and dyed fabric may be slightly flammable due to having hydroxychavicol in the chemical constituent of betel nut.

RMS of Peach Leaves (Figure 15): Semi-dried Peach leaves were plucked from Peach tree garden. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Minimum color strength is found but fastness is lightly higher, increasing dye percentage may improve the color on the fiber surface. Remaining ferrous, copper, and zinc may be responsible for coloring the cotton fiber. As per chemical constituent, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory can be found.

4. Method of natural fixing for mordant free dyeing

Maximum natural dyes sources from natural tree leaves, roots or fruits have ferrous ion, tannin, curcumin, catechin, OH group, and other known and unknown phytochemical constituent. Ferrous ion, tannin, curcumin, and catechin are making various color formations, and OH group is creating affinity with cellulosic fiber as well as the fastness properties may be increased if the dyes have natural pigment which may influence the capability of remaining dyes on the fiber surface after washing. Drying/curing with higher temperature may impact the color making duller or brighter. So specific dye-fiber system of natural fixing for mordant free dyeing is also possible but exact curing/drying temperature should be fixed for getting expected outcome of shading. So expected mechanism of mordant free natural coloration may be proposed as below although dyes and fiber substances may create changing of it.

5. Testing process

5.1 Color fastness to wash method

ISO 105-C06:2010, color fastness to water method: ISO 105-E01 and color fastness to light was tested by AATCC TM16 in Q-SUN XE-2 Xenon Test chamber.

5.2 Machine used for color parameters

Color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^* , Y) were measured by Hunter Lab Spectrophotometer, machine name: ColorFlex EZ, Model 45/0 LAV, Geometry

Figure 16.
Color Flex EZ, Spectrophotometer.

45°/0°, viewing area: large, visible spectrum (400–700 nm), testing condition: D₆₅/10°, room temperature of testing lab: 18°C (**Figure 16**).

6. Representation of dyed fabric and picture of dyes sources

All dyed shades were scanned with HUAWEI Smart Phone, Camera-13 MP, distance between fabric sample and camera position: 12–16 inch. So there is a possibility of having difference with actual shade. Picture of actual dye-fiber system was also scanned with HP Scanjet 4890 Photo Scanner. All sources of dyes pictures have been mentioned on the basis of grown trees in Asian Countries, specially in Bangladesh and scientific name was used accordingly. All the pictures of chemical structure mentioned here indicate the group of tree, not exactly indicating the chemical structure of specific parts of trees which one is extracted and dyed on cotton fabric.

6.1 Overcoming contradiction of natural dyeing

A huge number of researchers are working on natural dyes, still have a challenging for uneven dyeing, appropriate mordanting and dyes availabilities, shade matching where I can put a logic to protect our environment and human life as well.

6.2 Uneven dyeing

Automation in extraction and dyeing process.

6.3 Appropriate mordanting and dyes availability

Selection of specific dyes for commercial production and/or wastage can be used as dyes sources.

6.4 Shade matching

Customers are not always asking for shade matching when they are shopping although some natural dyes have attractive shading and repeated shading also possible.

7. Conclusion

Mordanting free coloration was practiced establishing the feasibility of environment friendly natural coloration which is the ongoing research of author and a part

of his research has been included here. Shade variation of natural dyed fabric may influence the uncontrollable factors for the collection of natural dyes sources on the basis of season to season, region to region and a same source but different parts of same dye sample source. So it is very tough to make a specific declaration of shading behaviors by the textile technologist but specific expertise in natural dyes extraction and natural dyeing may minimize the problem whereas expertise in dyeing with synthetic dyes and dyeing with natural dyes are not same for bulk production.

Following directions for the real shade development mentioned above:

1. Fabric should be well scoured and bleached.
2. Dyes materials should be clean, dried and powdered properly, improper drying and inappropriate powder formation may be responsible for unexpected shading and uneven dyeing.
3. Extraction time, dyes percentage may be maximized or minimized if the actual color is not observed.
4. Improper filtration of dyes may create uneven dyeing.
5. Dyes should not be powdered in wet or sticky condition which may effect the changing of light fastness and color shading.
6. Insect affected dyes source may create the changing of shade.
7. Synthetic mordanting and chemical medium dyes extraction may improve the shade but the concern of chemical and cost.
8. For open bath dyeing, liquor ratio should be higher, and stirred continuously to reduce color mark on the dyed fabric.

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